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Sampling the Trajectory Space of Chess

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A thesis submitted in partial fulfillment for the
degree of Master of Condensed Matter Physics

in the

Faculty of Science, Technology and Communication
Physics and Materials Science Research Unit

October 2016

“Nobody ever figures out what life is all about, and it doesn’t matter. Explore the world. Nearly everything is really interesting if you go into it deeply enough.”

Richard Feynman

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Abstract

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Rare event sampling techniques have been used to investigate the connectivity properties of the state space of chess positions. This work entails writing a client program anew for the rare event sampler SPRES [1] (Stochastic Process Rare Event Sampling), studying the connectivity properties of specific subspaces, modelling the sampled subspaces as random graphs, exploring their emergent properties and studying the resilience in connectivity of sampled regions with a proposed flow network model. Finally, by modelling chess in terms of statistical mechanics, certain aspects of its long term behaviour are characterized in a manner analogous to certain physical systems, e.g. the motion of Brownian particles or the glassy phase of amorphous materials.

In order to feasibly sample transitions in the state space of chess, an optimal reaction coordinate RC is proposed. By sampling various subspaces of positions obtained from random, similar and different openings, we establish an acceptance criterion for connecting pairs of arbitrary positions. This in turn allowed us to study larger subspaces by modelling them as random graphs. By studying these graphs, we found that the underlying subspaces are poorly connected, essentially populated with small isolated islands, without any sign of a strongly connected component. Furthermore, the model of flow networks allowed us to pinpoint the types of positions that cause a bottleneck in the studied transitions. But more importantly, it provides a natural setting for a quantitative assessment of the connectivity of two regions in the state space.

Finally, by studying the dynamics of chess, we show that with a number preserving map, chess pieces essentially behave similar to physical systems in a glassy state, with pawns acting as frozen disorder, leaving the remaining pieces to rattle in local cages and leaving some degree of correlation always locked into the system. Last but not least, we come to the conclusion that the irreversible and slow dynamics of pawns, the finite board size together with the topological limitations of same color pieces, make the long-term behaviour of chess strongly dependent on the initial condition.

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Abbreviations

TPS	T ransition P ath S ampling
RC	R eaction C oordinate
MSD	M ean- S quared- D isplacement
SPRES	S tochastic P rocess R are E vent S ampling
FEN	F orsyth- E dwards N otation
RGG	R andom G eometric G raph
KS	K olmogorov S inai

Symbols

RC	Reaction Coordinate distance	-
C	Overlap correlation function	-
L	Size of the symmetric set difference of moves	-
G	A graph	-
$V(G)$	Vertex set of G	-
$E(G)$	Edge set of G	-
\mathcal{S}	State space of chess	-
\mathcal{M}_1	Random, number preserving map of chess	-
\mathcal{M}_2	Random, complete map of chess	-

Chapter 1

Introduction

The game of chess is a two-player board game composed of a small set of sharply defined rules, that allow one to qualify a move either as legal or illegal. Despite the simplicity of its description, the game itself is highly complex, and luckily¹ it remains largely unsolved both from a game theoretic and a computational² point of view. This is mainly due to the rapidly increasing complexity of the game, as the tree of possibilities grows exponentially with number of moves, e.g. by move 10 there are about 10 trillion distinct positions that can arise.

As described by John von Neumann, chess is a zero-sum game with abstract strategy and perfect information. Today a large body of theory lies behind chess, as a result of years of ongoing struggle by theorists in an attempt to demystify chess strategy and come up with sets of concrete rules and principles that prescribe how each phase of the game should be played. Possibly one of the most successful attempts has been by Aron Nimzowitsch with his monumental work in the book of *My System*. Almost 70 years later, today modern chess seems to resemble anything but a principle-based game. In short, the advances in modern chess theory do not seem to adhere to any rule based model, and are strongly suggestive of a highly contextual game, with an emphasis on the fact that "no two positions are really equal" and the answer to "what is the best move here" lies solely in a careful and rigorous analysis of the position. This is not to say that all our attempts at understanding chess have been in vain, but it merely enunciates the unavoidable complexities of the game.

¹For chess enthusiasts...

²Some useful estimations: chess has a state space of size 10^{46} [2] and a game tree complexity of 10^{123} if assuming 35 as branching number (for 30 it is the Shannon number [3]).

In view of all this, chess players are nonetheless capable of devising strategies and predicting optimal moves with reasonable accuracy and in a consistent fashion. This astonishing achievement can be partly explained by the fact that the game of chess is a highly goal-oriented game: everything is ultimately aimed at checkmating the opponent's king. Thus in order to put this discussion into a perspective conforming with the essence of this work, we can say that: playing chess optimally translates into assigning high likelihoods³ to only a handful of lines of play and in turn dismissing the vast majority of the remaining possibilities.

In the same spirit, let us consider, what would happen if we relaxed the purpose of the game, from checkmating to simply reaching a certain set of positions, whilst leaving the rules of the game untouched. Would we still be capable of efficiently reducing the tree of possibilities down to only a handful again? Would it even in principle be possible to reliably establish whether the targeted positions are reachable⁴ under finite number of legal moves? While this modified version also shares the goal-oriented property, it remains unclear as to how the optimality criterion⁵ should be redefined here. Questions of this nature capture the essence of the study we have embarked upon in this project.

1.1 Objective

First and foremost the goal of this work is aimed at the question: "How connected is the state space of legal chess positions?"

This question can be reformulated in various ways, though not completely equivalent, but they do shed light on the aspects we are interested in:

- Given an arbitrary legal position, what fraction of the state space can be explored from that position given the basic rules of the game? Note that here by explore, we simply mean the set of positions that are reachable under a finite number of moves.
- From a physical point of view: How ergodic or non-ergodic is the dynamics of chess? For example adhering to how ergodicity is often defined, say we assign a macrostate by a certain set of pieces (e.g. 4 pawns and 2 kings), then we ask, given an arbitrary configuration of these pieces, what fraction of the total of possible

³In the parlance of importance sampling, optimal play highly biases the trajectories sampled.

⁴In contrast to how one knows which subsets of pieces are sufficient for checkmating.

⁵With checkmating as objective, optimal play means roughly: sound pawn structure, high mobility of pieces, safety of the king, controlling more space and covering essential pieces.

configurations remain reachable? Intuitively speaking, we clearly expect that for different starting configurations, the fraction will be widely different, since for example as soon as pawns are involved, their irreversibility and one dimensionality prohibits them from reaching a considerable number of positions that one can configure with the same piece set.

- From a graph theoretic perspective, thus here treating the state space of chess as a directed graph: Given an arbitrary pair of positions, what is the probability for them being connected by a valid sequence of moves? Or possibly more interestingly, what is the average size of the strongly connected components in this space? Meaning, given a random node n (assumed legal), if it is not a deadlock position (i.e. checkmate, stalemate), what is the average number of nodes with which n can communicate? (meaning there is a directed path for $n \rightarrow u$ and $u \rightarrow n$.)

As far as we know, the properties of the state space of chess in general, remain largely unexplored. Although there has been a great deal of interest in the actual count of the set of legal chess positions (since the works of Shannon [3]), they are all in essence combinatorial problems that do not concern with the question of connectivity, rather legality is of sole interest. Thus this work can also be seen as a first exploration into the state space of chess, where we propose and investigate various ways of probing the properties of such a large state space with unknown structure. But the main focal points of the work are: on the one hand developing a feasible sampling technique for chess, by extending the existing SPRES package and constructing an optimal reaction coordinate for sampling the trajectory space of chess. On the other hand, we put considerable emphasis on the study of the dynamics of chess under different time evolution maps, in order to gain insight on the long term behaviour of the system and be able to infer some of the connectivity properties of the state space.

1.2 Methodology

We mainly rely on various sampling techniques: on the one hand, we perform trajectory space samplings using SPRES in order to find reactive paths between pairs of positions, taken from a subspace of positions under study. This part is key to building the graph models and flow networks that follow. On the other hand, specially for the study of dynamical properties, we define various move generators, each associated to a different time evolution map of the game, under which we will measure, among others, the mean-squared-displacement (MSD) of pieces and overlap correlation functions between current and starting positions. These quantities are all averaged over many realisations of the same run (i.e. same initial condition, same generator and same move sequence lengths).

1.3 Structure

The thesis is structured as follows: In chapter 2, we give a brief overview of some of the theoretical notions essential to this work, then in chapter 3, we introduce the framework, which covers the translation of chess into a stochastic discrete-time dynamical system, a description of the state space of chess together with a new way of calculating the number of chess positions, a short description of the dynamics and an overview on the sampling methods adopted in this work. With these covered, we then move on to presenting the main results (chapter 4).

The results are two fold: the first part will cover the graph theoretic results, which is preceded by a section showing and discussing the SPRES sampling results. The second part will cover the results on the study of dynamics of chess, when treated as a statistical mechanics system. Each subsection of the results ends with a series of observations and conclusive remarks. Furthermore, in chapter 5, we discuss on the one hand, alternative ways of studying the state space, on the other hand, we include some of our results which proved to be rather interesting on their own, but they were not directly related to the main premise of this work. Finally, in chapter 6, we draw our main conclusions.

Chapter 2

Preliminaries

In this chapter we give a brief overview of some of the theoretical notions that form the backbone of this work.

2.1 Graph Theory

A graph, denoted by G , is a set of points often called nodes or vertices, together with a set of pairs of nodes called edges. Vertices are often labelled by letters such as n , and edges by the two vertices defining the edge, e.g. $e = \{n, m\}$. We say then the edge e or $\{n, m\}$ is incident on vertices n and m , and the two vertices are adjacent to one another. For undirected graphs, the order in which the edges are defined is not important, as $\{n, m\}$ and $\{m, n\}$ are equivalent. But for directed graphs, the order matters, as there may be a connection from n to m but not the other way around.

Thus to define a graph G , both its vertex set $V(G)$ and edge set $E(G)$ have to be properly defined. By definition the vertex set is a finite non-empty set, but the edge set can be empty. Often graphs are visualised by a 2D embedding, where vertices are represented by dots and the connections between them (edges) by lines. It is very important to note that graph visualisations do not qualify as accurate descriptions of a graph as they may exhibit properties beyond the underlying graph itself. For example the relative positioning of the drawn dots or the shape and length of the edges should not be interpreted as derived from the graph, unless it is stated so. The latter means that, certain vertex or edge properties may be included in the drawing of the graph, for example, one vertex property would be its degree, which is the count of the direct neighbours of the vertex, with the neighbourhood of a vertex v being defined as the set of vertices that are adjacent with v (for directed graphs, one distinguishes between

out and in neighbours), then one can encode this information about vertices onto the drawing, by e.g. drawing vertices as circles with their radii defined as a function of their degree.

The concept of equivalence of two graphs can be rigorously defined as follows: two graphs are assumed to be equivalent or isomorphic, if there exists a one-to-one correspondence between their respective vertex sets, added that the one-to-one correspondence also carries over the adjacencies (i.e. for each pair of adjacent vertices in one graph, the corresponding vertices have to be adjacent in the other one).

To finish this first overview, we give a select of important definitions of graph properties, that are of interest in this work:

- Order o of a graph G is the size of its vertex set, $o = |V(G)|$.
- Size s of a graph G is the size of its edge set, $s = |E(G)|$.
- A path in G : An ordered set of vertices $\{n_1, n_2, \dots, n_i\}$ and the corresponding edges between each two consecutive vertices $\{\{n_1, n_2\}, \{n_2, n_3\}, \dots, \{n_{i-1}, n_i\}\}$, where neither vertices nor edges are allowed to repeat. We say then the two end-points n_1 and n_i (often labelled throughout this work by A and B) are connected by a path p .
- A component (or connected component): a connected subgraph of G . That is, there is a path between any two vertices of the component.
- A graph is connected if there is at least one path for each unique pair of vertices. (Although in general a *walk* between each pair of vertices is sufficient to qualify a graph as connected.)
- Strongly connected component: An extension of the concept of components for directed graphs, namely a directed graph has a strongly connected component if for each pair of vertices u, v of the component, there is both a $u \rightarrow v$ and a $v \rightarrow u$ path. In such a case, we often say the vertices u and v communicate.
- Vertex cut: Given a connected graph G , a set of vertices $Q \subset V(G)$ counts as a vertex-cut if $V(G) \setminus Q$ leaves G disconnected (i.e. comprised of at least two partitions). Additionally a minimum cut set is a vertex-cut with minimum cardinality. An edge-cut can be defined exactly analogously, in terms of edges.
- The resilience of a graph to losing vertices, is a measure of its connectivity. More precisely, a connected graph G is k -connected if it has a minimum vertex cut with cardinality k . Again k -connectivity can be redefined analogously for edges, in which case it would represent the resilience of a graph to losing its edges.

2.2 Ergodicity

In the context of Markov chains, the notion of ergodicity remains rather intuitive, as it is solely defined in terms of the reducibility of the transition matrix representing the chain. If a Markov chain is irreducible then it is ergodic. Irreducible here means that if S is the state space of the chain, then every state in S is reachable from any other state in S .

On the other hand, in statistical mechanics and more generally in mathematical physics, the ergodic theorem, as firmly established by the works of John von Neumann and George D. Birkhoff, is a rather a more involved concept. In statistical mechanics the ergodic theorem translates into the equivalence of time and ensemble averages of a system's properties. More precisely if f is a function of the phase space coordinates (f being a measurable system property here), then a time average of f (for initial condition $x(0)$) taken over a sufficiently long interval $T \rightarrow \infty$, (this is to mean that the period over which the measurement took place is much longer than the characteristic time scales of the system) is equal to the ensemble average of f :

$$\lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T f(x(t)) dt = \int_{\mathcal{P}} f d\mu \quad (2.1)$$

With \mathcal{P} the phase space of the system and μ the Liouville invariant measure. The first assertion of the above definition is that the time averages exist except for a negligible set of points (i.e. such set of initial conditions has measure zero), and are independent of the initial condition $x(0)$. To relate the two concepts of ergodicity mentioned above, at least at a conceptual level, it is useful to substitute f in Eq. 2.1 by a characteristic function of a subset s of \mathcal{P} . Then the time average simply describes the average amount of time the system spends in s ¹, and it is equal to the size of the subset s (given by the Liouville measure here). Note that again, the above assertion is assumed to hold independently of the chosen initial condition in s .

A caveat is called for here: The concept of ensemble was used rather vaguely in the above discussions. In essence what is important, is the set of conserved quantities that define the macrostate of a system. The ensemble then, represents the set of all possible states of the system conforming with the same macrostate. For example the ensemble of all states with the same energy, is called the microcanonical ensemble.

¹Assuming here that the equations of motion have been solved for a set of initial conditions in the subset s , thus generating a flow in \mathcal{P} .

Another way of formulating the ergodic theorem, is by invoking the metric transitivity of the hypersurface² in \mathcal{P} over which the evolution of the system is defined (hypersurface is just another name for the ensemble of points representing the same macrostate). It is easier to start from the considerations of a non-ergodic system: A system is non-ergodic if the hypersurface on which the orbits of the system lie, are not metrically transitive. This means that the surface can be decomposed into at least two invariant sets with positive measure each. In this case, a phase function f will in principle assume different time averages on either of the decomposed sets. Naturally this may leave a bizarre impression of whether any physical system can ever be ergodic, since as soon as a secondary integral of motion (e.g. if momentum is conserved), independent of that of the energy is included, the surface of constant energy will undergo a decomposition (as the two integrals were assumed independent, thus cannot exhibit the same values everywhere on the surface of constant energy). This can be partly remedied by only considering normal phase functions, that is, functions that assume the same value for all the equivalent states in \mathcal{P} .³ For a comprehensive coverage of these notions, the reader is referred to [4] and [5].

Most important takeaway message from the above discussions, specially for our purposes, is the fact that if a system is said to be ergodic on a subset of positive measure in its state space, then the system's orbits, corresponding to any initial condition in the subset, will in principle explore all the points of that subset. Thus a first sign of non-ergodicity would be the observation of strong dependence of a system's long term behaviour on initial conditions. Moreover in chess, it remains non-trivial as to based on which board properties should one extract points from the state space, such that they remain part of the same component. In other words, component identification in the state space of chess is not trivial as little is known about its structure.

2.3 Transition Path Sampling

Transition path sampling [6] is easiest to understand as a generalization of the Monte Carlo sampling techniques of configuration space to that of the trajectory space. When sampling the configuration space of a system using a Monte Carlo scheme, in essence one is performing a random walk in the space of configurations. The success of the sampling lies in being able to bias the random walk such that each configuration is visited in proportion to its probability. Extending this idea to the trajectory space of a system means, first of all we will be dealing with sequences of configurations (trajectories), to

²for example a constant energy surface in \mathcal{P}

³in which case all the equivalent states lie on the same set after a metric decomposition, thus the system remains ergodic.

which a probability can be assigned. Then a similar random walk can be devised to explore the trajectory space, visiting each trajectory in proportion to its probability.

Moreover when sampling for specific transitions in the state space of a system, the starting and target regions have to be well defined. As in this work, we will denote the starting region A (the ensemble of points from which trajectories are shot at time zero) with $h_A(x)$ its characteristic function (1 if $x \in A$, 0 otherwise), similarly we denote the target region by B with $h_B(x)$. To each trajectory $X(t) = \{x_0, x_1, \dots, x_t\}$ a statistical weight can be assigned as follows (often called a dynamical path probability):

$$\mathcal{P}[X(t)] = \rho(x_0) \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} p(x_{i\Delta t} \rightarrow x_{(i+1)\Delta t}) \quad (2.2)$$

Where $x_{i\Delta t}$ denotes the configuration visited after i iterations (time steps), and ρ denotes the unconstrained distribution of initial conditions. Now in order to compute the reactive path probabilities (i.e. paths that connect region A to B), the dynamical path probability 2.2 is sandwiched by the characteristic functions of the end-regions (to assign a probability 0 to all non-reactive paths) and normalized by the partition function $Z_{AB}(t)$, i.e. the sum of all reactive path probabilities, which in a discrete setting can be written as $\sum_i h_A(x_0) \mathcal{P}[X(i)] h_B(x_i)$. Thus the reactive path probability is given by

$$\mathcal{P}_{AB}[X(t)] = \frac{h_A(x_0) \mathcal{P}[X(t)] h_B(x_t)}{Z_{AB}(t)} \quad (2.3)$$

Note that the probability functionals as defined in Eq. 2.2 or 2.3 concern all trajectories of same length t . Moreover the form of the transition probability $p(x_i \rightarrow x_{i+1})$ follows from the true dynamics of the system under study, e.g. in the case Markovian dynamics, the probabilities are then only a function of the current state x_i , or in the case of systems with reversible dynamics, the p 's are simply delta functions. But in general, when employing rare event sampling techniques, the sampled transitions are non-Markovian, as e.g. in SPRES (the rare event sampler we will use in this work), meaning subsequent transitions remain dependent on the history of the trajectories so far visited.

It is the purpose of transition path sampling schemes (such as SPRES [1]) to be selective towards reactive paths among the set of all possible paths (emerging from the starting region). This is rather a reformulation of the previous picture of biasing a random walk in the trajectory space with the importance region being here the ensemble of reactive paths. It must be said that e.g. in the case of SPRES, although each path is generated by the true dynamics of the system, the sampling is performed in a coarse-grained space, obtained by projecting all degrees of freedom of the system to what is called a reaction

coordinate. Thus one is in essence computing a symbolic path probability (i.e. in the partitioned space, as now many points will be represented by a single reaction coordinate value). These points will be made more clear in the next chapter. For a complete account of transition path sampling, we refer the reader to [7] and [6].

Chapter 3

Framework and theory

Here we show how chess can be modelled as a dynamical system such that the machinery of statistical mechanics can be applied to it. Essentially we are dealing with 32 particles (thus at least 32 degrees of freedom) allowed to move on a 8-by-8 square lattice.

The lattice $\mathcal{L} = \{(i, j) \in \mathbb{Z} \mid i, j \in [1, 2, \dots, 8]\}$ itself is comprised of two types of squares, black and white. Given \mathcal{T} the set of piece types, the set of starting pieces \mathcal{I}_0 is given by:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{T} &= \{\text{pawn (P)}, \text{knight (N)}, \text{bishop (B)}, \text{rook (R)}, \text{queen (Q)}, \text{king (K)}\} \\ \mathcal{I}_0 &= \{16 \text{ P}, 4 \text{ N}, 4 \text{ B}, 4 \text{ R}, 2 \text{ Q}, 2 \text{ K}\}\end{aligned}$$

Each piece type $t \in \mathcal{T}$, follows a unique displacement criterion. Pawns are the only pieces that move irreversibly, as they can only move forward either vertically or diagonally, the latter being allowed only when pawns are capturing another piece. Moreover, when a pawn reaches the last row (8th row for white pawns and 1st row for black pawns), it must be turned into a non-pawn piece other than the king. On the other hand, all non-pawn pieces are able to move reversibly, with bishops moving diagonally, rooks moving horizontally and vertically, queens and kings both moving as a bishop and rook combined, with the exception that kings only move one square at a time (unless the king is being castled, in which case it jumps 2 squares). Lastly, knights move by jumping 2 horizontal squares plus 1 vertical square or the other way around. But more importantly, unless their target square is occupied by a piece of the same color, no intermediate piece can hinder their moving.

The reversible particles/pieces¹ can be further divided into monochromatic and irreducible ones. The former is unique to bishops, and the latter stems from the fact that the remaining reversible pieces are in principle (e.g. given an empty lattice) able to visit every lattice site and thus the associated Markov process will be irreducible.

Furthermore, chess has a discrete time evolution, with each time step, corresponding to a single ply, i.e. either a piece-move by white or by black. In order to avoid possible ambiguities, a game of n moves in chess, corresponds to $2n$ plies.

3.1 The state space of chess

The state space simply put is nothing but the ensemble of all possible ways the pieces can be configured on \mathcal{L} . This description includes configurations with arbitrary number of pieces (with a maximum of 32 given by \mathcal{I}_0) and illegal configurations that do not conform with the basic rules of the game. The latter refers to the fact that, some configurations are impossible. Simplest examples would be configurations where kings are on neighbouring squares, or pawns being on 1st or 8th row for black and white respectively, without having been promoted, and so on.

Such examples immediately raise the following natural question: given that $|\mathcal{S}|$ is known, i.e. the full counting problem of possible arrangements of pieces has been solved, which fraction of \mathcal{S} actually corresponds to legal positions? Imposing a certain set of simple constraints on the combinatorial problem of counting configurations, we can start obtaining rough estimates or greedy upper bounds (e.g. the famous Shannon number for chess). One such estimation is shown at the end of this section.

As far as we know, the exact size of $\mathcal{S}|_{\text{legal}}$ is not known yet. Assuming we know exactly how many configurations are legally accepted, the next question becomes which fraction of them are actually reachable from the starting configuration of chess. This question is by far more interesting as it closely relates to the properties of collective dynamics of pieces. In a broader sense, the state space can be viewed as a random directed graph G , where the vertices correspond to the configurations and the edges to pairs of configurations that are connected by a series of legal moves. Then one can start attacking subquestions of legality and reachability, e.g. finding the largest component of G , maximum degree of vertices, the average connectivity for arbitrary subgraphs, and so on. Such questions are very much in the spirit of this work, as will be further elaborated in

¹Here and henceforth, the terms particles/pieces, configuration/position, trajectory/line and lattice/board will be used interchangeably.

later sections.

Regarding the question of reachability by legal moves, the general consensus among chess players is that two positions are connected unless it can be trivially shown otherwise. The triviality here refers to verifying a simple set of primary aspects of the board, e.g. pawn positions and structure, positions of kings, activated pieces, number of pieces, and so on. Given the starting position of chess, some examples of unreachable positions would be: having stacked up pawns on a file when no pieces have been exchanged yet, pawns being on first (for white) and last rows (for black), rooks/kings/queens/bishops being placed past the pawn structure when no pawn-move has been made yet, having the king under check by more than two pieces, a pawn promotion when no pawns have been exchanged, the list can easily go on. But for our purposes, we need to establish a formal way of assessing the problem of reachability, if ultimately we are interested in finding out more about the state space \mathcal{S} . This can be better understood in analogy with how one establishes the concept of connectivity for a classical system in statistical mechanics. Given a system with N degrees of freedom, and n integrals of motion in involution, the trajectory of the system is restricted to the intersection of the n conserved quantities manifolds. We say then, the resulting $2N - n$ dimensional hypersurface in phase space constitutes a connected² graph, whose vertices comprise the reachable states of the system.

At this point it would be fair to say that there are no obvious extensions of such concepts to the state space of chess, arguably because its underlying structure is not well understood. For example, without an assumed structure, how can one uniquely determine the neighbourhood of a point $s_i \in \mathcal{S}$? Should it be the set of points reachable by one legal move? or less restrictively the set of points that share a certain set of predefined properties with s_i .

In section 3.3.2, we will elaborate on our candidate choice of model for describing the state space, in view of the questions of connectivity. Briefly, we partition the state space into subsets, called cells, and subdivide the question of connectivity to that of individual cells and ensembles of cells. The partitioning is done by assigning a cell to the set of configurations that have the same exact pawn structure.

Before ending this section, as promised we show a simple way of finding estimates for the counting problem of legal positions.

²With some ergodic assumptions.

3.1.1 Number of legal chess positions via FEN combinatorics

Here we show a possible way of estimating the number of legal positions by using the famous FEN notation, which is a unique encoding for chess positions. This section is part of the results, but it is more fitting to the structure of the thesis to cover them here, as a follow up to the previous discussions on the state space. Note that for our purposes here, we are only interested in the portion of FEN sequences that concern the placement of pieces. An example for the starting setup:

$$\text{rnbqkbnr/pppppppp/8/8/8/8/PPPPPPPP/RNBQKBNR} \quad (3.1)$$

From left to right, we have the 8th row up to the 1st row of the board covered, each separated by slashes /, (small letters used for black pieces). Since the permutation of different rows leads to distinct setups, the separators can simply be dropped and we only have to deal with the complete string and count its possible arrangements, whilst discounting the ones that lead to invalid FEN's.

Some clarifications on the FEN notation:

- Since different positions of empty squares in the string lead to different setups, we replace the numbers in the usual FEN notation by spaces denoted by s.
- For example for a given row, 1N6 means the row is composed of sNsssss.
- Regardless of the initial piece set considered (with or without captures) the length of the string is constant (64), since in case of captures the lost piece is replaced by an s.

For example if we are to consider only the full piece set, the list of letters is:

$$[r, r, n, n, b, b, q, k, 8 * p, R, R, N, N, B, B, Q, K, 8 * P, 32 * s] \quad (3.2)$$

Thus the permutations of the whole 64-element-sequence from 3.2, legal and illegal setups together are:

$$p_1 = \frac{64!}{(2!)^6(8!)^232!} \quad (3.3)$$

Notice that we can express p_1 differently by doing the placements one after the other as follows:

$$p_1 = \binom{64}{32} \binom{32}{8} \binom{24}{8} \dots \binom{16}{2} \binom{14}{2} \dots \binom{4}{1} \dots \binom{1}{1} \approx 4.6 * 10^{42} \quad (3.4)$$

The latter form lends itself better to a constrained version of the counting problem. For simplicity, we do not distinguish between bishops of different colors, moreover neighbouring king placements are not accounted for, and finally pawn-promotions are not considered.

One of the simplest constraints to invoke is the pawn placement, i.e. we simply want to include in our counting the fact that pawns cannot be set on either 1st or 8th rows, since on the one hand white and black pawns can never reach the 1st and 8th respectively and on the other hand we are not accounting for promotions in our counting. To include this constraint, it is easiest to first place the pawns, then the remaining pieces, as the constraint only concerns the pawn placement. For a given piece set, with each piece count denoted by $p, P, n, N, b, B, r, R, q, Q, k, K$ (capital letters for white pieces), we have:

$$p_{\text{imp}} = \binom{48}{p} \binom{48-p}{P} \text{Multinomial}(62 - T, n, N, b, B, r, R, q, Q, 1, 1) \quad (3.5)$$

With $T = p + P + n + N + b + B + r + R + q + Q$. Since kings can never be removed from the board, the number spaces is always given by $62 - T$. The total count denoted by C , is obtained by simply summing over all possible piece sets, with the following bounds: $p, P \in [0, 8]$, $n, N, b, B, r, R \in [0, 2]$ and $q, Q \in [0, 1]$.

$$C = \sum_{p, P, n, N, b, B, r, R, q, Q} p_{\text{imp}} \approx 7.22 * 10^{40} \quad (3.6)$$

This is already a rather good estimate, with little constraints taken into account. There are both under and over estimations involved in the calculation presented above. One underestimation comes from not having accounted for promotions, which would change the summation bounds we have used here. Among overestimations, we have various elements, to name a few: we have not corrected for neighbouring king placements, the bishops of different color are not distinguished, when many pawns are all the board, roughly speaking, we should account for positions that would only be reached if pawns of different color were allowed to ghost walk through one another.

3.2 Dynamics

With the basic definitions given, we now look toward formally describing the dynamics. Bearing in mind that other than the basic evolution rules of individual pieces, we are not imposing any further constraints on the dynamics. Moreover chess can be considered as a dynamical system that is neither described by differential equations nor by recurrence

relations. Thus we decide to aim for a discrete Markovian description of the dynamics. It may be already helpful to point out, that computationally speaking, this simply means generating the set of legal moves at each time step, and randomly choosing a move among them, irrespective of the history of the current state of the board. If we are to consider individual pieces on an empty board for simplicity, then one can show that knights/kings/queens/rooks can be all be described by an irreducible Markov process. Furthermore, except for the knights, the remaining set of reversible pieces are also aperiodic i.e. the greatest common divisor of periods with which the piece can return to its starting square, is equal to one. These properties are particularly of interest as they lead to Markov processes with unique stationary distributions.

One possible path of continuation into the study of dynamics, would be to consider Markov processes defined from a collection of pieces, and study the emergent properties, given that the individual chains are well understood. Similarly one can translate the problem into a complex random walk study with the following properties:

- Multiple vicious³ random walkers on a 2D square lattice
- A multi-component system as not all walkers follow the same evolution rule
- An asynchronous model, i.e. at each time step one walker can move
- The lattice has both reflective and absorbing boundaries
- The walkers of different color can annihilate one another

While these are worthwhile studies on their own, here we adopt a more computational approach. On the one hand we are interested in the interplay of dynamics of different pieces, and how they shape the long term behaviour of the system. For example the fact that the full dynamics of chess is neither number preserving nor measure preserving (assuming \mathcal{S} is equipped with the counting measure) due to the irreversibility of the pawns, qualifies the system as dissipative.⁴ Moreover we consider the behaviour under different types of maps, by slightly perturbing the full dynamics of chess. For example the dynamics can be made number preserving by removing the possibility of exchange of pieces. This has drastic repercussions on the overall behaviour of the system, as now, the system can never be freed of its irreversible elements. This in turn means that as soon as any subset of pawns block one another, a permanent wall of frozen disorder forms, highly restraining the mobility of the remaining pieces, and ultimately subdividing the

³"vicious," a term coined by M.E. Fisher [8], meaning no two walkers can occupy the same site.

⁴In contrast to Hamiltonian dynamics being conservative, here we deal with a shrinking phase space volume as the system evolves. (e.g. by pawn moves)

board into two disjoint regions (for the majority of the cases at least).

In contrast to the previous picture, when considering the full dynamics, pawns tend to get annihilated quickly, this consequently means that the remaining pieces are in principle able to explore all sites of the board, in other words the non-ergodicity of the dynamics has partly disappeared. Finally all such variants of time evolution maps can be put next to the dynamics observed in real games, for comparison. This is of particular interest, since in real games the emergent pawn structures are highly biased towards optimal ones, namely those that at the same time provide reasonable coverage for the king and maximize the mobility of the other pieces.

Finally from a practical point of view, going down the path of the study of multiple random walkers is not an easy task by any means. Instead we decided to adopt a rather more physical approach, which goes briefly as follows: first we simplify the general map of chess by decomposing it into simpler maps (number preserving, full map without bias, engine biased map and real game play), the idea being that each of these maps captures a different aspect of the overall dynamics, thus it provides a finer treatment of the bigger underlying picture. For every map then, we look for different types of motion that the system may exhibit on different time scales. Additionally we also study how subsequent positions decorrelate themselves from the starting configurations, under different time evolution maps. The latter study is further decomposed into the decorrelation of nonpawns vs pawns. The ensemble of these ideas and approaches aim at a better characterisation of chess dynamics, as alternatives means of inferring some of the connectivity properties of the state space.

3.2.1 Quantities of interest

In this part, we briefly elaborate on the set of quantities we are looking to compute in order to compare the dynamics under different maps.

Overlap correlation function: A simple way of quantifying the amount of overlap between two given positions, would be to compute a correlation function of occupancy numbers n , i.e. assigning a positive contribution to squares that are commonly occupied in the two positions at hand. This can be further restricted to account only for those that are commonly occupied by the same piece. Thus we can for example compute pawn-pawn correlation functions, or pawn-nonpawn, and so on. Denoting the correlation function by $C(t_0, t)$, where t_0 is the starting point in time and t being the current one,

the average overlap correlation function is given by:

$$C(t_0, t) = \left\langle \sum_{i=1}^8 \sum_{j=1}^8 n_{ij}(t_0) n_{ij}(t) \right\rangle \quad (3.7)$$

where the double sum over ij covers the whole board, $\langle \cdot \rangle$ denotes an average over realisations and the occupancy numbers are given by:

$$n_{ij}(t, p) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if the square } ij \text{ is occupied by the piece type } p \text{ at time } t. \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (3.8)$$

Note that in the above we gave the more general definition of occupancy numbers, where the piece type is provided as an input, $n_{ij}(t)$ would be used if we are solely interested in the square ij being filled or empty.

Mean-square-displacement (MSD): Another way measuring the deviation of positions along a trajectory from a reference position (usually the starting one), would be to compute the mean square displacement MSD. On the one hand the time dependence of MSD would provide information on the existence of different time regimes (diffusive, ballistic, etc.) that underlie the dynamics, on the other hand it provides a means of capturing the slowness of pawn dynamics compared to the other pieces. The general definition of MSD for all the pieces, is given by:

$$\text{MSD} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\mathbf{r}_i(t) - \mathbf{r}_i(t_0))^2 \quad (3.9)$$

where $\mathbf{r}_i(t)$ is the two dimensional position vector of the i th piece at time t , in \mathbb{R}^2 with integer components. More precisely we are interested in the behaviour of MSD averaged over many realizations, which we will denote by $\langle \text{MSD} \rangle$. Similar to how the correlation function C was made to be piece-specific, the mean-square-displacement will also be made piece specific, specially when we want to compare the dynamics of pawns versus the other pieces.

Symmetric set difference of moves: In order to define a similarity function between pairs of positions, e.g. between subsequent positions of a trajectory, we take the symmetric difference between the sets of legal moves possible between the two positions, and for it to be color agnostic (since comparing legal moves after one ply is not meaningful because we would be only comparing white's moves vs. black's moves), the set s_i of moves at step i is obtained by listing all possible moves (within 1 ply) for both colors

regardless of whose turn it is, thus $s_i = \{\text{moves} \mid \text{legal for black and white at ply} = i\}$, similarly so for a subsequent position we obtain s_{i+1} . The resulting size L of the two sets by taking their symmetric difference would give an estimate for how similar the two positions are, the larger the size, the less they look alike. L is given by:

$$L = |(s_i \setminus s_{i+1}) \cup (s_{i+1} \setminus s_i)| \quad (3.10)$$

In order to form an intuition for the values that L can take, consider the starting position of chess, compared to the same position except with the d pawn being on d4, these two positions differ by $L = 12$ moves.

3.3 Sampling

For any large non-trivial system, such as chess, the number of possible configurations is astronomically large. Thus any attempt at a straightforward sampling of all the configurations would be impractical and ultimately in vain. Instead with a Monte Carlo approach, a sample of representative states (trajectories in our case, in other words, sets of states) is taken by performing a random walk in the trajectory space. Now the ultimate intent is that, given two confined regions of the state space, the trajectories we wish to visit with highest frequency are those that connect the two regions at hand. The challenge lies in the fact that the vast majority of the trajectories sampled would never even come close to the targeted region, and thus have negligible weights in view of the connectivity we want to establish. Such circumstances call for schemes that go by the name of importance sampling, which are used in order to bias the sampling towards the statistically important regions of the trajectory space.

The types of sampling tasks that we want to consider are four folded. First fold comprises a biased sampling of trajectories, where we are interested in finding reactive paths between two different regions of the state space. For this end, we employ an stochastic rare event sampling scheme called SPRES [1]. A basic coverage of SPRES is given in the subsections that follow. Next we consider two types of free sampling⁵ maps. First a number preserving map \mathcal{M}_1 (i.e. exchanges of pieces are not allowed) and a free sampling with exchanges \mathcal{M}_2 . Note that in either case, promotions are always allowed. Lastly we also consider studying real games, where then the sampling is performed on a relatively large database of games played by humans.

⁵Free sampling as in no bias is invoked on the randomly sampled trajectories.

3.3.1 Reaction coordinate

Given the previous discussions on sampling, the size of the state space of chess and game tree complexity of chess (growing exponentially with depth), some form of coarse-graining that would allow for a feasible sampling of the trajectory space of chess, is called for.

Coming up with an optimal reaction coordinate (for the system and type of sampling under consideration) is one such coarse-graining. Reaction coordinates are often employed in the study of conformational time evolution of proteins, where one is interested to sample from e.g. a folded state to an unfolded state of the protein. In order to be able to perform such sampling in a reasonable amount of time, a scheme of optimal dimensionality reduction came to rescue. The idea lies in projecting all the degrees of freedom onto one, namely the reaction coordinate (RC). Inevitably a great deal of information about the system is lost in the process. But often it remains possible to come up with a reaction coordinate that preserves sufficient information on the dynamics, such that the coarse-grained picture still contains relevant bits of the dynamics for the sampling task at hand. Three of the main criteria that a viable RC should fulfil are: it must reliably distinguish between the regions of the state space we want sample, this way the RC would at least potentially serve as a measure of progress between the two regions, secondly it must be an efficiently computable function of the configurations in the state space, and finally the RC should be optimal.

Optimality here boils down to how much overlap between points in the state space is created after the projection onto RC, clearly in the worst case scenario where almost all the points are projected onto a handful of RC points, the dynamics of the coarse-grained system become completely erratic (sometimes a poor RC is associated with fast kinetics), and the RC serves no purpose. An optimal RC on the other hand, would ideally be one that exhibits slow dynamics, as a result of smaller overlaps caused between different parts of the state space. For a rigorous treatment of optimality of reaction coordinates, we refer the reader to the following two works, [9] and [10].

In the field of transition path sampling, the ideal RC is the commitor [6]. Given a source region A and a target region B , the commitor is the probability of a point in the state space for reaching B before returning to its source A . Clearly such RC would not satisfy the second criterion previously mentioned. In fact often the commitor is itself a quantity of interest, when e.g. one tries to estimate transition rates between the two regions A and B . But more importantly, one cannot apriori know to which system observables the commitor is correlated. Unless one has additional information about the system's

transitions, e.g. if the sampling problem may resemble an already solved case. To give some viable examples of RC's, for example in protein-folding studies, the following quantities often serve as optimal RC's: root-mean-square distance from a reference structure (molecular conformation), number of contact points, radius of gyration, to name a few.

In what follows we will first say a few words about the adopted sampling scheme SPRES and then explain our choice of RC.

3.3.2 SPRES

SPRES [1] stands for Stochastic Process Rare Event Sampling. It is in short a computational method for sampling rare events. SPRES is of particular interest to us, as among the other existing methods, it provides a practical way of sampling and computing probabilities of rare events under nonequilibrium conditions, with irreversible dynamics.

It is important to point out that here the choice of sampling scheme stems from two important facts: First being that there does not seem to be any meaningful way of mapping the complex dynamics of chess to a free-energy landscape, as one would e.g. do for studying complex many-body physical systems, such as protein folding. Second reason is that we are not generally making assumptions on the dynamics of chess, i.e. we precisely intend to study the nonequilibrium states of chess, with nonstationary dynamics, without having to make steady-state assumptions.

The key idea in making the sampling feasible lies in the dimensionality reduction of the high dimensional state space via an optimally chosen reaction coordinate RC . That is, we project all the degrees of freedom onto a one-dimensional subspace S_λ spanned by the reaction coordinate value λ . Clearly the one dimensional space will not represent an accurate description of the actual state space, but for the purposes of sampling trajectories between subspaces of \mathcal{S} , a carefully optimized distance reaction coordinate will preserve the essential properties of the underlying configurations that connect the subspaces under study.

Once the reaction coordinate chosen, we bin the corresponding state space S_λ , such that the biased sampling is performed for the paths generated between subsequent bins of the reaction coordinate. Moreover the trajectory fragments are run in discrete fixed time windows, i.e. we deal with fixed fragment duration and fixed bins (i.e. the binned

RC values onto which we project visited configurations, remain constant in time), all of which makes the adaptive sampling between bins less cumbersome and the computation of the time dependent transition matrix more tractable.

Finally in order to achieve a constant number of forward transitions from each bin onward, SPRES performs an adaptive sampling, by varying the number of shots tried from each interface i at each time step t , and by a weighted selection among the candidate configurations of each bin based on the history of the trajectories, from which new shots will be thrown.

As our choice of optimal reaction coordinate, in analogy to one of the RC's for molecular systems, namely the root-mean-square distance from a reference structure, we propose here an RC that qualifies as a distance measure between two positions (points in the state space) under consideration. We first proceed by assigning an appropriate distance measure to each type of piece, then by taking a linear combination of the chosen distances, we define our RC.

Since our natural setting is a square lattice in the two-dimensional Euclidean plane, we define our distance measures as follows:

- The Chebyshev distance D_C is used for queens, kings and bishops. $D_C = \max(|\Delta x|, |\Delta y|)$.
- The Manhattan distance for rooks: $D_M = |\Delta x| + |\Delta y|$.
- For pawns $D_p = \Delta y$ without capture.
- And for knights, we take the ceil of half of the Chebyshev:

$$D_N = \lceil D_C/2 \rceil.$$

The reaction coordinate RC between two positions A (with piece set \mathcal{I}_A) and B (\mathcal{I}_B) is then given by:

$$RC = \begin{cases} \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{I}_A|} D_i & \text{if } \mathcal{I}_A = \mathcal{I}_B \\ > C & \text{with } C \text{ some constant, if } |\mathcal{I}_B| > |\mathcal{I}_A| \\ \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{I}_B|} D_i + \sum_{j=1}^{|\mathcal{I}_A \setminus \mathcal{I}_B|} v_j & \text{if } |\mathcal{I}_B| < |\mathcal{I}_A| \end{cases}$$

The constant C is a positive number chosen empirically, as a threshold, such that two positions with $RC > C$ can be reliably considered as disconnected. Finally the constants

v_j are positive numbers chosen differently for each type of piece, so as to punish uniquely for missing pieces.

It is important to note that the reaction coordinate we proposed in this section, did not arise from a series of trivial considerations, rather the final form of the RC as shown here, was obtained through a tedious process of trial and error. In this process, a first easy test for the optimality of the RC, was to study the time series of the binned RC, to see whether long periods of stationarity, erratic or discontinuous jumps could be observed, in which case the RC would likely qualify as a poor choice. Instead if the time series of the binned RC showed an increasing monotonic behaviour, it was a good bet that we were closing in on an optimal RC.

To give an example, the first versions of the RC, even for sampling between two very simple looking positions such as the two shown in Fig. ⁶ 3.1, were far from optimal as can be seen from the type of time series of visited RC-bins that were obtained, as shown in Fig. 3.2. In contrast with the later versions, we were closer to the desired monotonic behaviour, see e.g. Fig. 3.4 which was obtained for sampling between two very complex positions Fig. 3.3 (relative to the previous example, in terms of number of pieces and the structural change involved in reaching the target position). One such reactive path for this example (diagrams in 3.3) was:

1.Kh8 Rdf1 2.Qc5 Rfg1 3.Rd6 Bb3 4.Na6 Kd2 5.Nb4 Ba4 6.Ng8 Bd4 7.Rc8 Nc1 8.Nh6 Qf1 9.Qxc3+ Ke2 10.Bf6 Bxe8 11.a6 Kd1 12.Bh4 Bb5 13.Bf6 Qe1 14.Rdd8 Ba7 15.Qc6 Bb6 16.Rd6 Bf2 17.Nf5 Qc3 18.h5 Nd3 19.Qd7 Re1 20.a5 Re2 21.Ra6 Nc5 22.Bg5 Bg3 23.g6 Ree1 24.c6 Qd4 25.Raa8 Bd3 26.Nh6 c4 27.Bf6 Bf4 28.Rg8 Rhf1 29.Rgf8 Be3 30.Na6 Kd2 31.Nb8 Rb1 32.Qe7 Rbc1 33.Nd7 Ke2 34.Qd8 Kf2 35.Kg8 Be2 36.Bg7 Qd2 37.Ng4+ Kg1 38.Ngf6 Nb3 (Notice the starting exploration phase (RC flat), during the first 10 plies, until a clear progress towards B , namely the capture on c3, is made on move 9.)

⁶All the chess position diagrams in this work have been taken using Hiarc3 13.

FIGURE 3.1: An easy sampling example, to reach the position on the right from the starting configuration given on the left.

FIGURE 3.2: Time series of the visited RC bins, for 5 reactive paths between the positions shown in 3.1

FIGURE 3.3: A more involved sampling example, to reach the position on the right from the starting configuration given on the left.

FIGURE 3.4: Time series of the visited RC bins, for a reactive paths between the positions shown in 3.3

Chapter 4

Results

This section is structured as follows: we start by discussing our adopted sampling scheme as a means of probing various properties of the state space \mathcal{S} , then we explain how the obtained results can be used to actually assess the underlying connectivity properties, which on the one hand entails constructing a Gilbert type of random graph for the sampled subsets of \mathcal{S} , and studying the emergent properties during its evolution, and on the other hand we propose and showcase a scheme for building flow networks from the trajectory space sampling results. Then we will show how by computing the corresponding maximum flow, and estimating the resilience of the network to losing nodes/edges, we can quantifiably assess and compare how connected different regions of the state space are.

Then comes the main section on the dynamics of chess. The study of the dynamics is very much in the same spirit as that of the inverse problem in complex networks, which is about inferring topological properties of a network by closely studying the dynamics of the individual units. The idea to follow such a path in this work (which proved to be very practical and insightful), came after we realised some of the difficulties in trying to model the collective dynamics of pieces as multiple random walkers. The section on dynamics starts off with the mean-squared-displacement results and then follows the results on the overlap correlation functions.

Finally a separate section of results is added, called "other results and alternative approaches" 5, which contains some of the alternative continuations that we have either only proposed, or have only partially gathered results for. These include, to name a few: an alternative way of partitioning the state space that offers advantages for tackling reachability questions, a brief study of the build up of pressure on the pawns and distribution of pieces when evolving the system under a number preserving map, a showcase on how the symmetric set difference of moves can be useful as a way of comparing

the similarities of two positions and also capturing the interplay of pawn and nonpawn moves in terms of their respective influence on the emergent positions.

4.1 Implementation

Although the main focus of this writing is to report on the main results that were obtained during the two parts of the thesis, it is still important to at least mention a few words on the implementation side of things, after all they often turned out to be the more time consuming aspects of the work.

The first contribution was the rewrite of the client code used in the SPRES package. SPRES, as part of a larger software package FRESHS which contains implementations of various sampling algorithms, is composed of a server and client code. The former contains the sampling algorithm, whereas the latter, namely the client side is where the simulation method is implemented. Thus the rewrite of the client code in our case entailed: encoding chess positions, running chess dynamics (generating a valid trajectory fragment), computing various board properties including the reaction coordinate, filtering out implausible or undesired positions (i.e. handling exceptions) and returning properly formatted positions to the server side. Moreover, various scripts were written to complement SPRES, for the following purposes: post-processing the results (such as extracting trajectories with desired properties), automatising sequential sampling job and preparing the sampling set (extracting constrained positions from a database) to name a few.

Other than the rare event sampling implementations, random graph and flow network generations, various free samplers (number preserving, cell preserving, engine biased), database digestion and game extraction, to name a few, have been among the other scripts written for this work. All the implementations have been done in Python, with `python-chess` as the main chess library used for move generation and the random graph visualisations together with the flow networks were created using the `graph-tool` library for Python.

4.2 Sampling subspaces of \mathcal{S}

Given the tree complexity of chess, turning to importance sampling schemes becomes mandatory when trying to find paths connecting two arbitrary positions. Having previously explained the main working ideas of our adopted rare event sampling scheme,

SPRES, we start by explaining how the subspaces are chosen and how the sampling process goes.

The first part constitutes extracting a certain number of games, fulfilling certain constraints, from a chess database [11] of games solely played by humans. The latter is to ensure the validity of the picked positions (in the sense that by definition they are all reachable). The constraints may vary, but two core ones are: depth of the game (or a ply range) and the type of position, e.g. based on the opening that led up to that position. Our main emphasis in the extraction phase is on the types of positions, we are interested in three types of subspaces, comprised of: random openings, same or similar openings (among the selected lines¹ were: variants of the Sicilian defense, Ruy Lopez, Scotch, Queen’s pawn and the English opening) and different openings (e4 vs d4, e4 vs c4 and c4 vs d4).

To create a sampling list for each subspace, we select pairs of positions from the database, fulfilling the desired constraints, and add them to the list if the RC value of the pair is below a previously defined threshold δ . Now in order to probe the connectivity properties in each subspace, there are two main ways to go about it: either we only sample each picked pair or we randomly pick pairs from the list and sample those. The former case is what we have done in order to build the connectivity histograms, of RC and path length values for the pairs that were successfully connected by SPRES, and the latter case, along with the histograms, constitute the ingredients for building the random graphs, which we will get to after having shown the results of the histograms. Note that if we were to sample solely the picked pairs, the resulting graph, denoted here by G would have the following properties:

- Given r distinct pairs have been sampled, the order of G is $|V(G)| = 2r$ and its size $|E(G)| = N$ where N can at most be equal to r , reached when all chosen pairs are connected and $N = 0$ for the fully isolated case. As we sample each pair only once, the maximum vertex degree will always be one.
- If we repeat building such subgraphs, the set of vertices are randomly picked, and consequently the edge set is randomized for every newly picked set of vertices, since we cannot know which ones are connected beforehand. Point being that although G has some random properties, it does not necessarily fit into the class of random graphs due to the fact that our construction process has already fixed the emergent structure, namely a collection of disjoint edges and isolated vertices,

¹The number of picked pairs were not uniformly distributed over the selected lines.

thus for a given pair of order and size values, there is only one possibility up to isomorphism.

With this in mind, we propose the following for building *actual* random graphs: all we need is a set of n nodes (positions), a probability distribution over the set of possible edges (since the edges have to be directed, there are in total $n!/(n-2)!$ possible edges) and a graph size value of m in mind. The goal will then be to study how the structure of such a graph evolves for increasing values of m . The results concerning this part will be covered in section 4.3. Now we show the obtained connectivity histograms and elaborate on how they can be used to estimate the probability distribution of edges as a function of RC.

The following results are not updated with recent additional SPRES runs. (to be updated soon) In Fig. 4.1 we compare the full histogram of the starting RC values (for all the pairs of the 3 subspaces together) with that of the connected pairs (i.e. those for which SPRES could find at least one reactive path). First observation is that the majority of the pairs that survived the extraction phase, had an RC in the range of 5 to 25 (in arbitrary units of a square-side), when δ was set to 100 in the extraction phase. Note that RC values can also be defined in units of ply: to see this, it suffices to replace all the pieces by kings, then the distance between two positions in terms of RC becomes the same as the minimum number of king moves (thus plies) required to reach the target position. For the most part, except for very low values of RC, we observe that the RC-histogram for the connected pairs (in green) follows the same trend, hinting at the fact most of the pairs satisfying $RC < \delta = 100$ were indeed connected as verified by SPRES. The apparent breakdown of this fact for $RC < 10$ is a sign of pairs with almost identical setups except for small incompatibilities in their pawn structure that suffices to disconnect them.

In Fig. 4.2 the full RC-histogram is split into the contributions from each sampled subspace. The corresponding path length histograms are also shown in Fig. 4.3. As it may have been expected we see that on average the reactive path lengths are longer when the position pairs are from different openings, which is just a reflection of the fact that the structural change required to reach the target position is greater in this subspace, compared to that of the same openings.

Interpreting the RC values in units of ply as previously explained, we can compare the RC and path length histograms for the connected pairs. This is shown in Fig. 4.4. Intuitively speaking we expect that the larger RC is for a given pair, the longer

FIGURE 4.1: The normed frequencies on the y-axis are already multiplied by the bin-width. The blue histogram corresponds to the starting distribution of RC for a sampling list of 2246 pairs of games and in green the histogram of the 1624 pairs that were successfully connected by SPRES.

FIGURE 4.2: Normed frequencies such that the area under each histogram is equal to one.

FIGURE 4.3: The y-axis here denotes the actual frequencies.

FIGURE 4.4: Comparing the histograms of reactive path lengths with the corresponding RC's (in green).

the reactive path ought to be, and this is at least qualitatively observed in the joint histograms.

It must be noted that although we can feasibly sample between any two arbitrary positions using our importance sampling method, doing so for a large sample size would still be a rather time consuming process, moreover extracting the previously described subspaces from a chess database is in itself a demanding task as the majority of the picked pairs do not pass the desired constraints. This in turn means that in order to make any reasonable assessment about underlying connectivity properties of the state

FIGURE 4.5: With k the shape parameter and θ the scale parameter.

space, a simpler method for establishing whether two positions are connected, other than direct sampling, is called for. To this end we have adopted two alternatives:

- With a careful comparison between the RC histograms of connected pairs and the total sampled set, we can heuristically establish a threshold RC value below which the pairs are almost surely connected.
- We treat the RC-histogram as a probability distribution² over possible edges (as a function of RC), this way we can construct an acceptance criterion for edge placements, very much similar to Metropolis type of rules in Monte Carlo simulations.

The validity and usefulness of either of the above schemes is largely dependent on the amount of sampling used to build the histograms, for example it is important to work with a sample set uniformly defined over the whole range of RC values of interest (here from 0 to 100), such that the estimated proportions over each RC bin are obtained from similar sample sizes. An important advantage of these ideas is to overcome the need for direct sampling (similarly for the extraction phase), such that the connectivity properties can be assessed from a much larger subspace of \mathcal{S} .

²Although not necessary, but for the histograms showcased here, the connected RC-hist can be fitted with a Gamma distribution (see Fig. 4.5)

4.3 Random graph model

Given the set of vertices for one of the sampled subspaces, together with the edge probabilities estimated from the connected RC-histograms, to be used for constructing an edge acceptance criterion, we are now in a position to model the subspace of positions under consideration as a Gilbert type of random graph $G(n, p)$ (with n the number of vertices and p the probability³ of joining two randomly picked vertices). The construction goes as follows:

- Vertex set: n unique random positions (with possible constraints) are picked.
- The edge set of G is constructed by picking random edges among the $n!/(n-2)!$ possibilities, each pick being added to $E(G)$ with a probability $\propto p(RC)$.⁴
- For a target number of edges m , this process is repeated until m edges are successfully added to G .

Of special interest to us is the evolution of such a graph with increasing number of edges m , an idea often used in the study of complex networks [12]. Evolution here entails studying the emergent connectivity properties of G , for example the order of the largest component, the largest strongly connected component, number of components, average in/out degrees and centrality properties such as edge-betweenness, for increasing graph size.

4.3.1 A first look at the results for a random subspace

We first start by showcasing the obtained results for $n = 1417$ randomly picked positions, with the graph size m ranging from 0 to 800. Here the first of the two proposed approaches in 4.2 is chosen for edge placement, that is, all edges with $RC < \delta$ are accepted with the same probability, with the threshold δ set to 100. In Figures 4.6, 4.7, 4.8, 4.9 and 4.10 a series of snapshots (for $m = 30, 130, 310, 520$ and 800) of the evolution of the graph is shown.

From the snapshot we can clearly see that for low values of m , the graph constitutes essentially an ensemble of isolated, all on average small, components. This picture

³For typical Gilbert random graphs, p is just a parameter, namely the success probability of a Bernoulli process.

⁴Here no longer a parameter, but a probability distribution. But it is important to note that if we decide to use an RC-threshold as acceptance criterion, the parameter based model is retrieved.

FIGURE 4.6: Snapshots for $m = 30$

changes as the components start coalescing slowly⁵ at first, until the final snapshot where a clearly large component has formed, surrounded by the remaining smaller isolated islands.

A word of caution is called for here, as with graphs, visualisations come almost always with properties over and above that of the actual graph. For example in our case it is important to note that none of these components are necessarily *strongly* connected, that is, given two random vertices u, v in the same component, they do not necessarily communicate (i.e. $u \leftrightarrow v$). But the visualisation may lead one to conclude that the subspace under consideration is highly connected, which may be an acceptable first qualitative assessment, but a careful distinction will have to be made between the observed average

⁵The critical change in connectivity properties of G is not captured in these snapshots, this will be covered when plotting e.g. the order of the largest component as a function of m .

FIGURE 4.7: Snapshots for $m = 130$.

orders of *undirected* components and strongly connected components which accounts for the directedness of the edges.

Next we study a subset of topological properties of G as they evolve with varying number of edges. The comparison between the connectivity of different classes of subspaces (random, similar, or different openings) will be covered later, where for each class the vertex set will have to be renewed and the acceptance criterion updated. For now we only show the results for the random subspace of 1417 nodes. The following plots [4.11](#), [4.12](#) and [4.13](#) are obtained by averaging over 10 realisations of the graph G .

Let us start with the first observations: from Fig. [4.11](#), we clearly see that starting

FIGURE 4.8: Snapshots for $m = 310$

from low number of edges, up to $m \approx 400$, G does not undergo any critical change in its connectivity, which means that the graph is being populated by many small components, none of which seems to grow at a greater rate with respect to the others. This observation goes hand in hand with the fact that for low values of m , the majority of the added edges tend to connect previously disconnected nodes. A critical change in the connectivity of G occurs at $m \approx 450$, where a large component starts forming, due to a sudden increase in the coalescence rate of smaller components. This is a first clear deviation from the behaviour of random graphs⁶, where the critical change in connectivity is expected to occur at $m = n/2$ [13], which in our case would be $m = 708$.

⁶Note that here, we have not invoked the directed property of edges when identifying the components of G , thus our comparison here with *undirected* Erds-Rnyi random graphs remains valid.

FIGURE 4.9: Snapshots for $m = 520$.

As to how the number of components in G varies with increasing m , as shown in the plot 4.12, the number of components is decreasing linearly with a slope of 1, indicative of what was also previously observed, namely that for the most part the added edges tend to either connect two isolated nodes or coalesce two components together. A slight deviation from this linear behaviour may be observed for larger values of m , this is due to the fact that for $m > 450$, a large component starts forming, which together with the slow growth of the remaining components increases the probability of adding edges that connect two nodes of the same component and thus not contribute to the growth of any component. It must be noted that this effect is partly washed out in the averaging over multiple realisations of G .

In the discussions so far, we only assessed the connectivity of the obtained random

FIGURE 4.10: Snapshots for $m = 800$.

graphs in terms of their component properties. More importantly, our analysis relied on the assumption that the graphs are undirected, i.e. an edge $\{u, v\}$ connecting the node u to v , implied that v is also connected to u . Now we relax the aforementioned assumption and invoke the directedness of edges into our identification of components. This means we now refer to a proper subset of nodes in G as a component, *iff* there is a *directed* path connecting any two vertices of that component. The newly defined components are often referred to as *strongly connected components*. In order to study the effect of the directedness on the graph properties observed so far, we look at the plot of the order of largest connected component shown in Fig. 4.13. We see that for the same range of graph sizes as for 4.11, i.e. $m \in [0, 800]$ the graph G viewed in terms of its strongly connected components, is largely disconnected, as the size of the largest connected component fluctuates between 1 and 2 (i.e. only pairs of communicating nodes

can be found). More importantly, the previously observed critical change in the growth of the graph has now completely vanished.

It must be noted that the subspace under study here, is composed of randomly selected positions with little structural correlation between them, other than the bias introduced by the types of games that were collected in the database we are using. Thus one can argue that the observed loss of connectivity is rather expected given the irreversibility of pawn moves and captures. Any edge in G , involving either a pawn move or a capture is likely to be unidirectional (although there may be exotic cases where a backward path can be devised, these do not fit into the bigger schemes of things). This means that in essence, it is possible to start from an arbitrary point in \mathcal{S} , and connect to many other points via pawn moves or loss of pieces, but the resulting connectivity holds only in one direction. In the scope of the above observations, we can say that, due to the dissipative dynamics of chess, the state space is bound to be populated with small (w.r.t. the size of the state space) isolated islands.

The results presented so far are not complete yet, the project is still ongoing as we are still accumulating results, with the following points in mind:

- To redo the graph with a much larger vertex set (i.e. including more recent SPRES sampling results).
- To redo G for different types of subspaces (the results covered so far were only for a random subspace without constraints on the openings) and compare the emergent connectivity properties.
- To redo G for subspaces of different plies, to compare how the connectivity changes for various depths of the game, i.e. as we move down the tree of moves.
- **Most importantly:** The evolution of G needs to be studied for a wider range of graph sizes, i.e. $m > 800$. (specially for the plot of Fig. 4.13, to see whether this constant behaviour changes at any point.) Admittedly the literature on the evolution of *directed* random graphs ought to be looked into more closely, for a better assessment of the observed results here.

4.4 Flow networks

For a more complete and algorithmic treatment of flow networks we refer the reader to [14] and for a brief introduction, to the lecture notes in [15].

FIGURE 4.11: ($n = 1417$) Growth of the largest component as a function of number of edges m .

FIGURE 4.12: Number of components as a function of m .

In this section we show how flow networks, as a model of choice, together with our sampling capabilities developed in this work, provide a straightforward means of quantifying the connectivity between two nodes or regions of \mathcal{S} .

The idea goes as follows: Our working graph now is obtained from the set of unique positions that are visited during the sampling of the trajectory space, in order to connect two positions A and B . This means that the number of vertices in our graph will be highly dependent on the average length of reactive paths on the one hand, and on the mobility of the pieces in the starting position A on the other hand. The latter simply means that the lower the mobility in A , the more likely it is for the trajectories to

FIGURE 4.13: Order of the strongly connected component of G , averaged over 10 realisations.

fluctuate back and forth between a small set of positions, and thus fail to generate a sufficiently large subset of positions. Although this will probably remain unimportant for the majority of positions A that one might consider. (assuming that within few plies the position will have sufficiently deviated from A , such discussions will be part of the section on dynamics)

Given the generated set of positions obtained during the search of reactive paths as our vertex set $V(F)$ (with the two vertices A, B as source and sink), and the edge set $E(F)$ extracted from the sampled trajectories, we define our directed graph F of the flow network. The remaining question is, how do we define the capacities, as edge-properties, in order to complete our flow network model. A simple solution, similar to how edge capacities are defined for geometric networks, would be to take the capacities as inversely proportional to RC. With an added upper threshold, we define the capacity c_i by

$$c_i = \min(1/RC(i), \epsilon), \quad \forall i \in E(F) \quad (4.1)$$

where ϵ can for example be set to 10. Such a flow network model serves various purposes, all of which revolve around computing the maximum possible flow from source to sink:

- One strong reason for computing the maximum flow, is the max-flow min-cut theorem, which will allow us to identify the bottleneck in transitions from A to B , for the sampled trajectory space. Then through a careful characterization of the underlying positions responsible for the bottleneck, we will have pinpointed the key differences (or similarities) between A and B that render the two as poorly

(or highly) connected. Moreover repeating the max flow computation for various sets of sources and sinks, provides a quantitative comparison of their connectedness, without requiring a precise estimation of transition rates, which can be a computationally more demanding task. (one reason being that, to have reasonable confidence intervals for the estimated transition probabilities between any two subsequent interfaces of RC, a large number of reactive paths have to be sampled for.)

Two important caveats: in either case, whether we use SPRES results to estimate transition rates or we use them to compute max flows, how reliable the subsequent comparisons are, depends in both cases on the optimality of the reaction coordinate. In the former case, this optimality translates to how much overlap is RC introducing between the points in \mathcal{S} , and in the latter case it translates to whether the current definition of RC is an acceptable connectivity-criterion.

The second caveat is regarding the comparability of max flow results obtained for different sets of source and sinks. In general the reactive paths found by SPRES for different A and B 's will be of different lengths. This may then create normalization issues as the flow calculations naturally depend on the volume of trajectory space that has been sampled. One way to resolve this would be to set a minimum length condition, that ensures a sufficient portion of the trajectory space has been sampled. How much ought to be sufficient is of course a question that remains to be thoroughly studied.

- Alternatively the edge set $E(F)$ can be defined anew by adopting one of our previously suggested schemes for modelling subspaces of \mathcal{S} as random graphs. This way, given the generated vertex set $V(F)$ by SPRES, instead of extracting the edges from the sampled trajectories, all edges satisfying $RC < \delta$ are added. The advantage being, without having to let the sampling process run longer in order to explore a larger portion of the trajectory space, we now have an exhaustive edge set, from which we can find the remaining (potential) reactive paths that can be constructed given the vertex set $V(F)$. The main disadvantages are: firstly, the fact that we are back to using RC as our sole criterion, which may lead to an overestimation of the connectedness between A and B , secondly, this estimation is also dependent on the size of the vertex set. Finally the presumed additional reactive paths that we may find, will come with varying lengths (with any path composed of at least 2 edges being allowed), moreover we lose our previous mapping between *number of edges* and *number of plies* of a path.
- Another useful aspect of flow networks is the connection it provides between the minimum cut set (vertex or edge cut) of the network and the maximum number

of disjoint paths (vertex or edge-wise) connecting the source-sink. This is more generally formulated in terms of Menger's theorem (will have to check how extensible the theorem is for directed graphs). In our case, the Menger's theorem can be leveraged if we set all the edge capacities to unity, in which case computing the maximum flow reduces to finding the minimum cut sets, i.e. the minimum number of vertices or edges that have to be removed in order to disconnect the source from the sink. This provides a way of assessing how resilient our set of reactive paths are to losing vertices or edges, something that can also be used as means of comparison for connectivity of different regions A and B in \mathcal{S} .

Below we showcase a first application of the max flow approach: the sink and source positions are shown in Fig. 4.14, the corresponding directed graph is comprised of both the vertex and edge sets being obtained directly from SPRES samplings (i.e. no application of RC-based criterion in this example). Furthermore to complete the flow network, the assigned edge-capacities are computed as a function of their RC, using Eq. 4.1.

Some assumptions: we are only considering feasible flows through the network, i.e. all edge flows $f(e)$ are bounded on both sides by $0 \leq f(e) \leq c(e), \forall e \in E(F)$, moreover the flow through all vertices $v \in V(F) \setminus \{A, B\}$ is conserved, meaning that if $O(v)$ and $I(v)$ denote the set of out-neighbours and in-neighbours of vertex v respectively, then

$$\sum_{u \in O(v)} f(v, u) = \sum_{u \in I(v)} f(u, v) \quad (4.2)$$

The above assumptions imply that the net outward flow from the source (often called the *value* of a flow) will be equal to the net inward flow of the sink, which can be written as: (with A : source, B : sink, '+' denoting net-flow leaving a vertex and '-' net-flow entering it.)

$$f^+(A) - f^-(A) = f^-(B) - f^+(B) \quad (4.3)$$

Finally in order to compute the maximum flow feasible through this network, we use the Ford-Fulkerson method [16], before explaining what the method entails, we first need two essential definitions:

Definition 4.1 (Residual network). Given a flow network comprised of the vertex set V , edge set E together with a capacity function $c : V \times V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_0^+$ and a feasible flow f ,

the corresponding residual network is comprised of the same vertex set but its edge set is now defined by all the pairs of vertices (u, v) for which the following holds

$$c(u, v) - f(u, v) + f(v, u) > 0.$$

Definition 4.2 (Augmenting path). For a given flow, an augmenting path is a path from source to sink in the corresponding residual network.

In short the Ford-Fulkerson method goes as follows:

- Initialize the flow f from zero.
- While an augmenting path can be found in the corresponding residual network, increase the flow f along that path.
- If no further augmenting paths can be found, the corresponding flow value will be equal to the maximum flow.

The maximum flow through the sampled network for A (source) and B (sink) as shown in Fig. 4.14 is computed. Most important is to identify what types of intermediate positions are causing the bottleneck of transitions from A to B . For this specific example, having computed the max flow, the notable edges in the minimum edge cut, were all those that involved the return of the bishop from the f4 square to white's queen-side (as this involves two main pathways that are easily blockaded).

Had the return taken place right at the start of reactive paths from the source, the bottleneck would potentially be reduced as there is already an open path for the bishop (d6, b4, d2, c1 right from A), but as it happened during the sampling, first the easy transitions started occurring successfully (namely Nc3, Qd6-to-b6, ...) all of which reduced the RC (between the instantaneous positions and B) thus were favoured by SPRES. These observations emphasize the order dependence of transitions in the state space of chess, which can only have a negative repercussion on the degree of connectivity, as the more important the order of moves is, the less probable will the corresponding reactive paths become.

It would be extremely interesting to study the flow networks of, on the one hand similar (in structure) openings and on the other hand openings assumed (by chess players) largely dissimilar (as in no reasonable transposition between the two exists), and compare their flow properties in order to pinpoint what aspects of the involved structures dictate the connectivity. As part of this thesis, we have only showcased one example of the application of flow networks. These studies remain part of the ongoing works of the

FIGURE 4.14: The position chosen as source on left, and as sink on the right.

project, where quantities such as max flow, source of bottleneck, number of disjoint paths, number of paths found as function of sampling time, and so on, are being studied for a wide range of different positions.

4.5 Dynamics of chess

Given the main objective of this work, namely exploring how connected the state space of legal chess positions is, it is natural to leverage the strong duality (though not in a strict sense) that exists between the topological properties of the state space and the dynamics of collective pieces. To put it differently, given a point in the state space, the size of the space reachable from that point is solely given by the rules governing the evolution of individual pieces and their collection thereof. Thus here we set out to study the dynamics of chess more closely, by borrowing ideas from statistical mechanics and dynamical systems, in order to ultimately infer some of the underlying properties of the state space.

The results that follow are mainly divided into two parts, one evolving around the behaviour of the mean-squared-displacement (MSD) of the pieces and subsequent to that we have the study of the overlap correlation function, both studies repeated and compared under different conditions and time evolution maps. This brings us to the different maps we chose to work with, which we cover here before presenting the results.

The idea of changing slightly the evolution map of the game, in order to discover what repercussions they may have on the long term behaviour of the game, can reveal a great deal of insight on the actual, full dynamics of the game. This is very much analogous to how sometimes the dynamics of a physical systems is perturbed, in order to figure out

FIGURE 4.15: Early stages (ply ≈ 10) of evolution under \mathcal{M}_1 .

under which conditions, can the dynamics become ergodic.

Below we give a list of the various maps we have chosen to work with, along with the adopted notations:

- \mathcal{M}_1 : (map 1) Number preserving (without captures), and without bias (random and independent generation of moves). A select of snapshots of the type of positions that occur with \mathcal{M}_1 , for the 3 stages of, early, mid and end (for 3 randomly selected trajectories) are shown in Figs. 4.15, 4.16 and 4.17 respectively.
- \mathcal{M}_2 : (map 2) Full dynamics, but again *without* any bias in the move generation. Snapshots of early, mid and end stages are shown in Figs. 4.18, 4.19 and 4.20 respectively.
- Cell preserving: Given a partition of \mathcal{S} , these classes of maps do not allow the system to evolve out of its starting cell. (e.g. if a partition is defined by fixing the pawn structure, then no pawn moves would be allowed, this is covered in a later section, 5.1).
- Full dynamics *with* bias: e.g. using a rare event sampler (here SPRES).
- Full dynamics, biased under *optimal* play, e.g. by invoking a chess engine on either of the random samplers $\mathcal{M}_{1,2}$.

In the following subsections, under various conditions such as different initial conditions or density of pieces, a subset of states are evolved in time under the different maps previously mentioned, and the quantities of interest (MSD and the correlation function C) are computed and averaged over many realisations of the same experiments.

FIGURE 4.16: Mid stages (ply ≈ 45) of evolution under \mathcal{M}_1 .

FIGURE 4.17: Near end stages (ply ≈ 1500) of evolution under \mathcal{M}_1 .

FIGURE 4.18: Early stages (ply ≈ 10) of evolution under \mathcal{M}_2 .

FIGURE 4.19: Mid stages (ply ≈ 45) of evolution under \mathcal{M}_2 .

FIGURE 4.21: The two initial conditions (left: IC 0 and right: IC 1) for which MSD is to be computed.

4.5.1 Mean Squared Displacement results

We start with the MSD (for definition see Eq. 3.9) results obtained for constant density (set at maximum, $\rho = 0.5$, defined as the number of squares occupied over the total number of squares), but for two different initial conditions (IC) of pieces. One being the actual starting setup of chess (which we will denote by $IC = 0$) and the other a typical position that can emerge from the Scotch game ($IC = 1$), the corresponding diagrams are shown in Fig. 4.21. The choice of the initial conditions is rather intuitive: the starting position since we are interested in exploring the part of state space that is legal and reachable given the starting setup of chess, and the second choice is to create a sufficient contrast with that of the starting setup, since in this Scotch variant, all the minor pieces along with the kings and queens are already activated.

The plots obtained using \mathcal{M}_1 and running 500 trajectories (each of length 2000 plies) from each IC , are shown in Fig. 4.22 (with linear scale axes) and in Fig. 4.23 (the log-MSD vs log-ply plot, along with the log-derivative of the log-MSD plot, i.e. $d \log \langle r^2 \rangle / d \log(\text{plies})$ vs $\log(\text{plies})$). The derivative is computed via a central finite difference method.

We see that the MSD eventually levels off towards a plateau region past the initial 250 plies, which is rather expected since on the one hand evolving the system with \mathcal{M}_1 means that past a certain point in time the pawn structure freezes permanently⁷, leaving the remaining pieces stranded on different sides of the board, on the other hand the board is finite, thus imposing an unavoidable upper bound on the MSD.

The separation caused by the intertwined pawn structures highly restricts the deviation of subsequent positions from their initial configuration, such that in the majority of cases the pieces will not be able to explore the whole board. This in turn means that the average localization length around each piece (obtained from the plateau values of MSD) ought to be considerably lower than what would be expected on a free board without obstacles, namely the upper bound imposed solely by the finite size of the board. The latter can be estimated by starting from the expression of the mean-squared-displacement for diffusive motion in arbitrary dimension d , namely $\langle r^2 \rangle = 2dDt$, where D is the diffusion coefficient. Now due to the finiteness of the system, $\langle r^2 \rangle$ is expected to level off at long times ($t \rightarrow \infty$). That is, in the long run the extent of the exploration of the pieces is given by the board size L , as $Dt \leq L^2$. This leads us to the following upper bound for the localization length, corresponding to the case where pieces are able to explore the whole board: $\langle r^2 \rangle = 2dL^2 = 256$ with the dimension $d = 2$ and board length $L = 8$ ⁸ in both directions. Instead, the observed plateau value, as expected from the above discussion, is $\langle r^2 \rangle \approx 10$ (for $IC = 0$).

Moreover we see a clear dependence between the plateau values and the initial conditions, implying that the long-term structures⁹ that can form will tend to remain distinguishable for different starting conditions.

On the other hand looking at the log and log-derivative plots (Fig. 4.23), in search of a potential power law behaviour ($\langle r^2 \rangle \propto t^\alpha$), we notice that the system evolves in a ballistic manner at first ($\alpha \approx 1$), which can be explained by the fact that during the first few moves the pawns develop freely and do not feel the presence of the other pieces, this is analogous to ballistic motion of Brownian particles at short time scales as they have not yet felt the molecular forces from the surrounding fluid or the friction forces. Then α decays slowly towards a diffusive regime (at ply ≈ 30) which again in analogy to Brownian motion, means that the motion of each piece is now controlled by its neighbouring pieces. Finally with the pawn structure settling in eventually, playing the role of a permanent frozen disorder into the system, the system enters a subdiffusive regime,

⁷At which point they will only have a constant contribution to the MSD.

⁸In arbitrary units of a square side of the board.

⁹such as the neighbourhood of each piece.

FIGURE 4.22: $\langle r^2 \rangle$ denotes the computed MSD averaged over 500 realisations, for the two IC's.

where the pieces are essentially rattling in local cages around themselves.

Next we look at the MSD of nonpawn pieces vs pawns, with the aim of capturing the slower dynamics of pawns with respect to the other pieces. The results for \mathcal{M}_1 and $IC = 0$ are shown in Fig. 4.24. The perfect convergence of the blue curve is a consequence of having used \mathcal{M}_1 . Other than the fact that we do not really observe a Brownian motion (although the pieces were set to evolve randomly) type of behaviour, we do see that specially for the period preceding the plateau, the pawns' MSD increases with a much smaller slope, capturing exactly the slowness of pawn dynamics in comparison to the minor and major pieces.

Finally we look at the log-log and log-derivative of the log-MSD plots for \mathcal{M}_1 and $IC = 0$ under different density conditions. The result is shown in Fig. 4.25. We mainly observe a super-ballistic ($\alpha > 1$) motion during the first plies at lower densities, nonetheless they all enter the subdiffusive regime eventually (although at different rates), but they converge towards different plateau values, higher towards lower densities as the remaining pieces have higher mobility and thus are able to explore a larger portion of the board.

Some conclusive remarks: We could see that the MSD captures information on rather many important aspects of the dynamics of chess and the longterm behaviour:

- The average localization length $l = \sqrt{\langle r^2 \rangle_\infty}$ is dependent on the initial condition, at least so for the number preserving \mathcal{M}_1 map.

FIGURE 4.23: Top: the log plots, middle: derivative of log of MSD, bottom: zoomed in on the derivative plot.

FIGURE 4.24: MSD of nonpawns (green) and pawn (blue) for $IC = 0$ and map \mathcal{M}_1 . On the bottom the semilog plot is shown.

- Focusing on different time scales, different types of motion could be observed, starting from ballistic, to diffusive and eventually subdiffusive. The trend being imposed by the caging effect of pawns, due to their initially slow dynamics, and to their 1-dimensional motion that ultimately leads them to a frozen setup, causing a permanent division of the board.
- Looking at the behaviour of MSD at lower densities, we clearly see that the localization length increases with decreasing density as one would expect. But rather surprisingly, even at the lowest density shown here, namely $\rho = 0.1$ (amounting to 6 pieces on the board), the saturation values of MSD at long times remain considerably lower than that of the free board ($\langle r^2 \rangle \approx 20$ instead of the previous trivial expectation of 256.). One explanation, among others, is the inherent topological

FIGURE 4.25: M_1 , $IC = 0$, for different densities.

limitations of pieces of the same color, that underlies the reduced mobility of pieces even in the absence of pawns. (Note that with \mathcal{M}_1 this effect is essentially being amplified, making the dynamics color agnostic, except for the fact that no piece can be moved consecutively twice in row, which is just another way of seeing the turn-based character of the game)

- Finally, in view of all these observations, it is safe to say that, although the pieces were set to evolve randomly, with an added restriction to be number preserving, it is rather the finiteness of the board, the topological limitations of same-color-pieces together with the collective set of peculiar rules¹⁰ that define how each type of piece can move, that render the dynamics highly non-ergodic. This is to the extent that even at very low densities, some pieces remain highly localized, either due to their neighbourhood or due to their own intrinsic dynamics.

4.5.2 Overlap correlation function results

In this section we review the results obtained for the various overlap correlation functions. Similar to how the results of mean-squared-displacement were obtained, we now compute the correlation functions, with respect to a given initial condition, averaged along trajectories generated by a map under consideration. For the purposes of this section, we will be working with the same set of initial conditions as before, moreover we are interested in the comparison of the maps $\mathcal{M}_1, \mathcal{M}_2$ and the optimal play map (for which we simply extract trajectories from a chess database [11]).

To calculate the correlation functions, denoted by C from now on, we use the equation 3.7 that was previously defined. But it is important to note that we are now interested in the individual correlation functions, given by the respective overlap numbers:

$$n_{ij}(t, p) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if the square } ij \text{ is occupied by the piece type } p \text{ at time } t. \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Overall we will be interested in the pawn/pawn, nonpawn/nonpawn¹¹, pawn/nonpawn and nonpawn/pawn correlation functions, whose sum accounts for all types of correlations and thus amounts to the total overlap correlation between two positions. We are specially interested in the comparison of the pawn/pawn and non-pawn/nonpawn correlation functions. The reason being that these two quantities will

¹⁰Irreversibility of pawns, discontinuous jump of knights, the bias introduced with king moves when under check, color-restricted bishops, to name a few.

¹¹Clearly for a finer study, this correlation function would be further split into: bishop/bishop, knight/knight, bishop/knight,

FIGURE 4.26: Top: linear scale axes, bottom: semilog plot. Illustration of the correlation function for \mathcal{M}_1 and $IC = 1$.

suffice for a complete distinction between irreversible and slow pawns vs the reversible and fast nonpawn pieces.

Before getting into the discussion of the main results, to gain an intuition on the various correlation functions, we plot together all C 's for \mathcal{M}_1 and $IC = 1$, shown in Fig. 4.26. The fact that all the curves level off towards a constant non-zero value can be argued as a typical behaviour of number preserving maps for finite systems. Additionally we notice in this example that the nonpawn pieces decorrelate faster than the pawns, but this is specific to the chosen initial condition ($IC = 1$) here. All these points will have received proper clarification by the end of this section.

Similar to the structuring of the MSD results, we will begin with the comparison of the

FIGURE 4.27: Top: linear axes plot, bottom: semilog plot. The total correlation functions for $IC = 0, 1$

FIGURE 4.28: Top: linear axes plot, bottom: semilog plot. Nonpawn/nonpawn correlation function for $IC = 0, 1$

correlation functions for different initial conditions ($IC = 0, 1$). In the following figures 4.27, 4.28, 4.29, 4.30, and 4.31 we show the linear and semilog plots for each correlation function.

Key observations made from the comparison of the correlation functions for different initial conditions:

- Given the previous discussions of MSD on how different types of motion can be identified on different timescales, we had made the observation that ultimately at longer times, the system becomes highly subdiffusive, due to the finite board

FIGURE 4.29: Top: linear axes plot, bottom: semilogx plot. Pawn/pawnn correlation function for $IC = 0, 1$

FIGURE 4.30: Top: linear axes plot, bottom: semilogx plot. Nonpawn/pawn correlation function for $IC = 0, 1$

size, the caging effect of neighbouring pieces of the same color and the frozen pawn structure, which leads up to expect that the total correlation functions *do not* vanish even at very long times. This is exactly what we can observe from Fig. 4.27, with both curves decaying and converging to non-zero values, the lowest being here for $IC = 0$ with $C_\infty \approx 11$. This observation alone leads us already to a rather interesting statement: If the time evolution map of chess is made number preserving, it becomes impossible to fully decorrelate from the starting configuration.

- Moreover we do observe different plateau values of C_∞ for the two initial conditions. The reason for this will become clear in the next points with the discussion of the

FIGURE 4.31: Top: linear axes plot, bottom: semilogx plot. Pawn/nonpawn correlation function for $IC = 0, 1$

individual correlation functions. But it suffices to say that the different C_∞ values can be used as means of distinguishing between classes¹² of positions, capturing useful information on the underlying structure inherent to the initial condition that does not fully vanish. In other words, with \mathcal{M}_1 the subsequent position will unavoidably contain some information on the specific starting setup.

- For the nonpawn/nonpawn C , as shown in Fig. 4.28, two main observations can be made: first that both curves decay roughly to the same value $C_\infty \approx 5$, which can be interpreted as the average number of nonpawn pieces that are correlated, second observation being the faster decay rate of the blue curve ($IC = 1$) which can be trivially explained by the fact that in comparison to the starting setup, in $IC = 1$ almost all nonpawn pieces are already activated and only partially restrained by the pawns.
- In the pawn/pawn case, the curve of $IC = 0$ decays to zero as all the pawns are free to move forward (in fact they will start with a ballistic motion as we saw previously), whereas for $IC = 1$, $C_\infty = 4$ which is equal to the number of frozen pawns in the starting setup.
- Finally regarding the nonpawn/pawn and pawn/nonpawn correlation functions: the former (Fig. 4.30) is always zero for $IC = 0$ as the pawns starting on the 2nd and 7th row, cannot move backward to occupy any of the nonpawn starting squares on the 1st and 8th row respectively. In contrast, with $IC = 1$ there are already 4 knights that have been developed to squares accessible to pawns. On the other hand, for the pawn/nonpawn correlations Fig. 4.31, the $IC = 0$ reaches the

¹²Classes as in proper subsets in \mathcal{S} , as C_∞ is not uniquely assigned to points in the state space.

higher plateau value as in principle after the wall of pawns has eventually formed, the starting 16 squares (for $IC = 1$ there are only 12 squares which can correlate pawns and nonpawns.) previously occupied by them will become fully accessible to nonpawn pieces.

Next we study the dependence of the overlap correlation functions on density of pieces. The first related figure, for the total correlations at different densities (\mathcal{M}_1 and $IC = 0$), is shown in Fig. 4.32. Although we do retrieve the expected picture of decreasing correlations with decreasing density (as simply there are less pieces to correlate with), it would nonetheless be more insightful to look at the plateau values of the individual correlation functions as a function of density. This is shown in Fig. 4.33.

It is interesting to note that the pawn/pawn overlap correlations always decay to zero, regardless of the density of pieces. Of course this goes hand in hand with the irreversibility of pawn dynamics, which prohibits them from having positive contribution to the pawn correlations in time. Only exceptions being, when opposite color pawns visit each others' original squares. But this is impossible with the map \mathcal{M}_1 as pawns would have to ghost walk through one another (this scenario does not change for different densities, as only pawns on same file can become correlated when using \mathcal{M}_1). Other exception worth considering would be a pawn promoting to another piece and return to its original square, but that would rather contribute to the pawn/nonpawn correlation function. (This is a very curious picture, since we are essentially saying the pawn correlates with its promoted image, but nonetheless the total possible correlation will not exceed the number of pieces on the board, meaning even with promotions, it is not possible to correlate two positions more than their total number of pieces.)

Finally we come to the comparison of the behaviour of correlation functions under different maps and fixed initial condition ($IC = 0$). Let us start with the comparison of \mathcal{M}_1 and \mathcal{M}_2 . As shown in Fig. 4.34, unlike \mathcal{M}_1 , when allowing for captures to take place, the system is able to fully decorrelate from its starting configuration. Of course with kings always remaining on the board, the nonpawn correlations do not completely decay to zero. But the king vs king setup is ultimately the equilibrium position under \mathcal{M}_2 dynamics, though it is not always reached as there are deadlocks in the state space, such as checkmate and stalemate positions.

Moreover we can see that the pawn/pawn correlations for either map, behave essentially similarly. Intuitively speaking this can be explained as follows: at the starting phases of the game, pawn-moves are the most probable (which is in line with the starting ballistic motion), additionally their likelihood of being captured increases as they expose

FIGURE 4.32: Total correlation functions drawn for various densities. In the legend, ρ denotes the density of pieces and pl the corresponding plateau values.

FIGURE 4.33: Normalized C_∞ values of each correlation function plotted as a function of density. Other than the pawn/nonpawn, the correlation functions have been normalized by their starting value. Whereas the pawn/nonpawn values are normed by their maximum value, namely $\min(|\text{pawns}(\rho)|, |\text{nonpawns}(\rho)|)$.

themselves in the center of the board, all of which to say that pawns tend to decorrelate themselves well before becoming targets to opposite color pieces. Of course we could have easily predicted this following our previous observations (in 4.33) on the independence of pawn/pawn correlations with density.

An almost similar argument can be given for nonpawn correlations, but with some differences: during the first 50 plies, with the majority of nonpawn pieces being still on the board (see the red dotted curve in 4.34), the two maps yield the same exact results. But as \mathcal{M}_2 is not number preserving anymore, past a certain point, nonpawn pieces start being captured (reducing the density) and in turn freeing more space on the board, which allows the remaining pieces a larger localization length and thus the rattling of pieces in local cages is not reproduced anymore. Ultimately with no pieces other than kings left, the nonpawn correlations also decay to zero.

Another similarity between the two maps is the fact that the red (nonpawn) and green (pawn) curves retain their relative positions with respect to one another. More precisely the decay rate of the pawn/pawn correlation function is greater than the competing non-pawn/nonpawn correlation. This highlights the interplay of reversible and irreversible pieces, where unlike the irreversible pawns, the reversible ones (all nonpawns) are in principle able to contribute positively to their respective correlation functions.

Another interesting observation can be made related to the pawn/nonpawn and non-pawn/nonpawn curves for \mathcal{M}_1 : they converge to the exact same value (here $C_\infty \approx 5$).

FIGURE 4.34: Comparison of overlap correlation functions computed under \mathcal{M}_1 (full lines) and \mathcal{M}_2 (dashed). The dotted curves correspond to the second Y-axis, showing average piece count under \mathcal{M}_2 in time.

This can be explained as follows:

For $IC = 0$ we know that all the nonpawn pieces occupy the 1st and 8th rows, and all the pawns occupy the 2nd and 7th rows. Additionally we now know that even with \mathcal{M}_1 pawns will completely and quickly decorrelate from their starting configuration, which implies the 2nd and 7th rows will completely free up past a certain ply t_0 . The point t_0 describes exactly the moment the pawn/nonpawn and nonpawn/nonpawn curves start overlapping, as past t_0 , the board has already divided into essentially two disjoint parts, leaving the nonpawn pieces on either side free to equally often explore the 1st and 2nd (or 7th and 8th) rows. Hence they will in principle be able to correlate themselves as much¹³ with their own original squares as with the original pawn squares. Finally it is important to note that these observations are not expected to hold for arbitrary initial conditions.

Next we compare the \mathcal{M}_1 map with the dynamics of real games (taking trajectories from chess databases [11]), previously denoted as *optimal play*. The corresponding plot is shown in Fig. 4.35. Some information about the plot: the curves for real games were obtained by averaging over 10000 games, and the range of comparison is now limited to 120 plies, as there are not many real played games that go past 60 moves (The average game length is ≈ 80 plies, thus 60 moves or 120 plies is still well within reach in terms of what game lengths can be found in databases.)

¹³In all correctness, unlike the boundary sides, the 2nd row is reachable both from the above and below.

FIGURE 4.35: Comparison of overlap correlation functions computed under \mathcal{M}_1 and optimal play, over a range of 120 plies. Full lines: \mathcal{M}_1 , dashed: optimal play and dotted lines correspond to the second Y-axis, showing average piece count under optimal play.

We see that up to ply 30, i.e. during the first 15 moves of the game, the blue (all piece) curves have complete overlap, as the majority of the pieces are still on the board, additionally players tend to favour occupying the center with their pawns first, creating space and coverage for the activation of minor pieces, and more importantly they tend to avoid redundant moves, e.g. retreating a piece to its original square, which implies the correlation functions are less likely to have positive contributions during the first 30 plies.

More interestingly, by comparing the red and green curves, we can clearly see that the previous observation regarding the faster (with respect to nonpawn/nonpawn) decay rate of pawn/pawn correlations is no longer preserved past ply ≈ 25 . This is due to the fact that players often favour a conservative pawn structure, in order to keep their future options open (as any pawn move comes as commitment), and instead the minor/-major pieces start dancing around the established pawn structure, thus leading them to decorrelate faster than pawns, in contrast to what was observed under the \mathcal{M}_1 evolution of the game. Moreover the latter interplay is further amplified, since around the same point into the game, the nonpawn pieces become more prone to exchanges.

As a last comparison we look at the correlation functions obtained for \mathcal{M}_2 and real games. The corresponding plot is shown in Fig. 4.36. Here we focus already on the more interesting bit, namely the comparison of pawn/pawn and nonpawn/nonpawn overlap correlation functions. In view of the previous discussions regarding the rate of exchanges of pawns and nonpawns being toppled past a certain ply (25 – 30) in real games, with

FIGURE 4.36: Comparison of overlap correlation functions computed under \mathcal{M}_2 and optimal play, over a range of 120 plies. Full lines: \mathcal{M}_2 , dashed: optimal play and dotted lines correspond to the second Y-axis, showing average piece count under \mathcal{M}_2 and similarly the dash-dot lines for real games.

\mathcal{M}_2 this is no longer observed. This captures the bias introduced in optimal play during the liquidation phase of nonpawn pieces, whereas with the map \mathcal{M}_2 , moves are generated randomly, thus as the pawns are first in exposing themselves to opposite color pieces, pawn captures will remain more likely throughout the evolution of the game. Ultimately, with only few pieces left, all correlation functions decay in principle to zero for both maps under consideration, of course with the important exception that under optimal play the absorbing states (checkmates) in \mathcal{S} gain considerable likelihood in their occurrence.

Some conclusive remarks:

- The idea to split the general map of the game into a set of simpler maps proved to be rather useful, as each map captured a unique aspect of the overall dynamics of the game. For example with \mathcal{M}_1 , we showed that without captures it is practically impossible for the system to fully decorrelate itself from its starting configuration. For our purposes this fact translates into saying that in general the dynamics and longterm behaviour of chess are highly dependent on the initial condition. This on its own is a strong sign of non-ergodic aspects of the game.
- The source of such non-ergodic properties are: most importantly the caging effect due to the topological limitations of the same color pieces, specially as the pawn structure establishes itself on the board as a permanent frozen disorder, in turn

also limiting the interaction between opposite color pieces (this is not inherent to \mathcal{M}_1 , as for example even in optimal play, as soon as a subset of pawns of both colors become intertwined and cause a partial disconnect on the board, they reduce the mobility of pieces or even completely hem them inside the structure). The latter properties along with the finite size of the board were successfully captured by the non-vanishing correlation functions.

- Moreover we saw that an increased density of pawns has no effect on the long-term behaviour of the pawn/pawn correlation functions, in contrast to the other pieces, for which a higher density always translates into higher long-term correlations. This is a rather important aspect in view of the connectivity of \mathcal{S} , as it highlights the following: the ensemble of points $p \in \mathcal{S}$ that satisfy a certain density condition $\rho(p) = c$, (with c being e.g. 0.5), are very likely to constitute a poorly connected graph, as their long-term behaviour, if they are to preserve their density, remain dependent on their respective initial conditions, thus it is increasingly more difficult to connect two positions u and v if they contain a high density of pieces. In other words, the set of positions generated by shooting many trajectories from both positions u and v , are expected to have little overlap.
- On the other hand, we saw that if we are to make the dynamics exhibit ergodic properties, e.g. by slightly perturbing \mathcal{M}_1 , say for simplicity into \mathcal{M}_2 , then although starting from any state, the system would in principle be able to become fully uncorrelated from its starting setup, it would only do so at the cost of introducing yet another non-ergodic property to the dynamics, namely loss of pieces, which irreversibly reduces the number of degrees of freedom of the system. Thus such attempt would be in vain.
- Ultimately, in view of the last two points, the full dynamics of chess, although composed of components which are individually ergodic (say queens, knights, rooks, kings on an empty board) and components that are highly non-ergodic (pawns), remains in general highly non-ergodic, with non-trivial collective dynamics. The system is only ergodic when confined to certain proper subsets of \mathcal{S} . For example, the ensemble of all points with a given density but without any pawns, evolved under \mathcal{M}_1 (even then there will be many deadlocks in the trajectory space of such subset caused by the kings). Additionally, for certain realisations of the frozen disorder of pawns, the remaining pieces can in principle be sufficiently mobile to explore the rest of the board, and in turn explore all the points in \mathcal{S} conforming with the disorder under consideration.
- The last point can be generalized in the following sense: pathways between arbitrary regions of \mathcal{S} tend to easily jam due to highly localized pieces (which itself is

in part due to the finiteness of the board and same color pieces hindering one another's motion) and the irreversible dynamics of pawns. These elements together, limit the system's ability to undergo the required structural changes, necessary for reaching a target position at hand.

- It may be more promising to look for local ergodic properties¹⁴, the locality emerging e.g. from a certain partition of \mathcal{S} . One such partition would be that of the pawn structures as will be covered in 5.1. Briefly, appropriate partitions allow to easily locate regions of \mathcal{S} that are likely to contain large strongly connected components (large with respect to the size of the region itself).

¹⁴This may leave a bizarre impression as to why one should look for regions in \mathcal{S} where the system becomes ergodic in the first place. The reason is that, by finding such regions we are in essence pinpointing parts of the state space that are strongly connected.

Chapter 5

Other results and alternative approaches

This section contains a series of alternative continuations and approaches that we have considered and partially gathered results for, but since their merit in view of the premise of this study still remains unclear, they are not included in the results section.

5.1 Partitioning the state space

We partition the state space \mathcal{S} into cells C_i of different sizes. The cells are disjoint ($C_i \cap C_j = \emptyset$ for $i \neq j$) as each cell corresponds to a unique pawn structure, i.e. given a pawn structure p_i , its corresponding cell is given by

$$C_i = \{s \in \mathcal{S} \mid s|_{\text{pawns}} = p_i\} \quad (5.1)$$

From the definition of C_i it follows naturally that the union of all cells cover the entire space \mathcal{S} as a priori we impose no restrictions on possible p_i 's. Thus given k the total number of cells, the previous statements can be written as

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^k C_i = \mathcal{S}. \quad (5.2)$$

With such model, we can now consider various iterations of a starting configuration c_0 under different maps \mathcal{M} . For example one can study the iterations of c_0 within its own cell, this is of interest when we want to study the dependence of the dynamics on the initial condition, or if we want to estimate the size of a cell. Alternatively one can consider

a map that iterates between cells, which results in a symbolic dynamical sequence over the cells. To clarify, say $c_0 \in C_0$, then after n iterations of the map, we have a trajectory of cells, $c_0 \rightarrow C_0, C_1, \dots, C_n$. Clearly the number of possible iterations n is dependent on the starting cell. Similarly the sequence of cells visited will also be a function of both the starting point and cell.

The above points highlight the usefulness of such partitioning, as it provides a natural setting for studying the dynamical properties of chess (such as ergodicity).

5.2 Pressure equilibration for number preserving maps

Here we show that when evolving the system under \mathcal{M}_1 , the pressure that builds up in the system with formation of the frozen disorder, is equi-partitioned on both sides of the wall of pawns. Moreover we map the rate of the formation of the wall, with the decay of pawn move probabilities.

The pressure p on the white and black pawn structures is computed by counting the number of nonpawn moves (color agnostic) that coincide with pawn positions (of a given color). As always these are averaged over 500 realisations each constituting a trajectory of 2000 plies. As for the interpretation of the numerical values of the pressure, notice in the plot 5.1, at ply 0, both curves take off from 14, which is the starting number of collisions between nonpawn moves and pawn positions for $IC = 0$.

Finally in the two plots of Fig. 5.2, a second Y-axis is added representing the probability of pawn moves (both sides together). This is of interest as it can be interpreted as an indicator of the progress in wall formation, when evolving the system under \mathcal{M}_1 .

From Fig. 5.2 we can clearly observe that the pressure on both pawn structures evolves identically, both before and after the wall formation, i.e. we do not see any bias in the distribution of pieces for either side. The pressure keeps increasing steadily as the wall is forming (i.e. white pawn move probability $\neq 0$), which goes hand in hand with increasing mobility of nonpawns, then it starts settling toward a constant plateau value (≈ 20) once the wall is permanently fixed.

FIGURE 5.1: Time evolution of the pressure on the white and black pawn structures respectively, under \mathcal{M}_1 and for $IC = 0$.

5.3 Some results with the symmetric set difference of moves

Taking the symmetric set difference of possible moves of two positions (denoted by L or 'Delta Symdiff'), is yet another way of measuring how dissimilar the two positions are (so e.g. if L is increasing along a trajectory, the overlap between the set of available moves of consecutive positions is decreasing.). The calculation was previously explained in subsection 3.2.1, Eq. 3.10.

For this study, we randomly extracted ≈ 43000 trajectories (that lasted up to ply 80) from a chess database [11] of games played by humans, and measured L for all the consecutive positions in a trajectory, then averaged over all the extracted trajectories.

As we can see in the Fig. 5.3, at the early stages of the game, $\text{ply} \in [0 : 6]$, the pawns are the character deciding components of the position, as with each pawn move, a small yet non-negligible subset of minor/major pieces become activated. Whereas any nonpawn move, which is likely to be by knights at the early stages, will have little influence on how the set of available moves changes from one position to the next. This behaviour is completely toppled at ply 6, past which the majority (on average) of nonpawn pieces are already activated, and have an important contribution to the total set of available moves at every moment in time. This means, further pawn moves will have little effect on the mobility of the remaining pieces, this of course goes hand in hand with the slower dynamics of pawns, as they can never hop between different regions of the board, and

FIGURE 5.2: Top: linear axes, bottom: semilogx. The second Y-axis denotes the probability of pawn moves. Results shown only up to ply 500 here.

in turn perturb local neighbourhoods of other pieces.

Finally, for the later stages, starting already at ply 7, the two curves undergo a large deviation, with the red curve (pawns) slowly levelling off towards an average of $L = 3$, whereas the blue curve (nonpawns) maintains its steady increase, which can be explained as follows:

On the one hand when there are only a handful of pieces left (near endgames), any minor (knight, bishop) or major (queen, rook) piece move will make a clear distinction between the two positions, as the board is largely empty thus the remaining pieces will have maximal mobility (e.g. a rook will have 14 available moves), which translates into

FIGURE 5.3: L (on the y-axis here referred to as 'Delta SymDiff') averaged over 43593 real played games, for the first 40 moves (80 plies). Bottom: A zoom-in on the first 10 plies.

larger values of L (intuitively the same interpretation follows from the fact that when only a handful of pieces left, the overall structure and character of the position is largely dependent on each piece). On the other hand when the position is still highly populated (middlegames), and these are rather the trivial cases, unlike pawns, any nonpawn move will in most cases have an influence on a large fraction of the board, and not only on its local neighbourhood, and since the density of pieces is still high, many pieces will have their set of available moves perturbed. All of which suggests that, in middlegames, with high density of pieces, as the game progresses, more and more pieces become mobile (on average), which translates into larger deviations in L for subsequent positions.

5.4 A possible random geometric model

Having established an optimal distance reaction coordinate, one can turn to other graph models. An example of a random geometric graph is showcased here.

In the 2D Gilbert model of random geometric graphs (RGG): A domain E of finite size is chosen in \mathbb{R}^2 , then a random point process is chosen (e.g. a Poisson process) in order to pick n points in the domain of E , two such points are joined if their distance is less than some parameter r . The metric used is the Euclidean norm in the plane.

Unlike Gilbert's model, where a meaningful drawing of the graph is possible, in our case a drawn diagram will only serve as a visualisation aid, as it may have properties over and above those consequent to their being graph representations of our model. For example the distances between the vertices after a random 2D embedding have no correlation with the actual distance between the positions the vertices represent.

In our case, we have different options for the metric we intend to use for measuring distances between pairs of vertices. The current version of the reaction coordinate itself is a valid choice as it satisfies the main axioms of a metric, namely that:

1. $RC(u, v) \geq 0$ for all $u, v \in V(G)$
2. $RC(u, v) = 0$ iff $u = v$
3. It satisfies the triangular inequality $RC(u, w) \leq RC(u, v) + RC(v, w)$. It is arguable whether it really satisfies this condition, but one reason that suggests it does, is: the RC has the transitivity property of closeness, meaning that for two vertices u and v that are close, if a vertex w is close to v , then u must be close to w as well.

One property that is not satisfied by RC is the symmetric one, as we have directed edges. With this approximate metric and graph model in mind, inspired by Gilbert's RGG, one possible line of progress would be as follows:

- We introduce first a small version of the model: we restrict the model to a circle (or square) of diameter d , such that the diameter (maximum eccentricity) of our graph G is d ($diam(G) = d$). In this domain we randomly embed n vertices corresponding to random positions picked from our database that all satisfy the imposed diameter condition.

- The advantages of the smaller model are: By construction all the chosen positions are relatively close to one another, thus our sampling takes very little time, and this allows to increase n to improve our statistics. The parameter r chosen to decide whether two vertices should be joined or not, is taken empirically. Once one such graph has been sampled for and characterized, we then enlarge the initial domain by changing ($diam(G) = d, 2d, 3d, \dots$) and add new sets of vertices satisfying the renewed conditions, and study how the properties of $G(d, r)$ change.

Such model would ultimately be a useful and worthwhile study, as it paves the way towards answering some of the important questions one can ask about \mathcal{S} , for example:

- What is the average connectivity of G , e.g. the average degree of vertices?
- Since we deal with a directed graph here, it may be interesting to look at the distribution of the in and out degrees.
- What is the largest component of the graph? Is it a clique? What do the positions in different components of G have in common?
- What are the maximum and minimum degrees of the vertices? Are there any interesting hubs in the graph? (this is more in the direction of dynamics)
- Do we have complete subgraphs? if yes what are their sizes? (which we expect to have, e.g. considering the set of positions that do not differ by pawn structure and piece set, thus they all have a chance of being interconnected).
- For each graph, if n is too large, we choose a reasonable subset of it for sampling, and gauging the error committed by our empirical choice of the parameter r .
- In Gilbert's RGG model, it is expected that by increasing the size of the domain, the connectivity increases, it should be interesting to find out how the connectivity behaves with the size of domain in our case.

5.5 Average information production per iteration step

This section covers an alternative approach to studying the properties of the general map of chess. So far it remains only a proposal, its merit towards better understanding the connectivity in \mathcal{S} remains uncertain. (in other words, it is not obvious how in general the chaotic properties of a map relate to the structure of the underlying state space of a dynamical system, of course in the cases where a system is integrable and thus the map completely regular, even the topology of the state space follows from it, but as far as I understand for general maps this is not a given.)

5.5.1 Context

Generally speaking, in the context of dynamical systems (chaotic or regular), one often refers to the average information loss or gain per iteration step of a map by its Kolmogorov-Sinai entropy, i.e.: (*The following section is mostly based on part 5, chapter 14 of [17]*)

Given a partition C ($\{C\} = \{C_1, C_2, \dots\}$) of the state space \mathcal{S} , we consider a map m for the coarse-grained dynamics over the partition. That is, the map m generates a symbolic sequence s of type i_0, i_1, \dots determined for a given initial condition $x \in i_0$, where the i_n 's are the cells in which the system finds itself after an iterate n .

Now we define a set L , containing all the initial conditions that can generate a certain symbolic sequence s given the map m . With an appropriate probability measure, we can then associate a probability to each allowed sequence, i.e. $p(s) = p(i_0, \dots, i_n) = \int d\mu$ where μ can e.g. be the counting measure.

Using the Shannon entropy here to measure the information in p , we have $H_S = -\sum_s p(s) \ln p(s)$ where s are the ensemble of all allowed sequences. It is clear that for any map m that we may be interested in, H_S will depend on the measure μ , the length of iterations and the partition C used. Formally speaking the definition of Kolmogorov-Sinai entropy KS , which is essentially the average information production per iteration step of m , i.e. $KS \propto H_S/N$, gets rid of the of the last two dependencies by assuming infinite iterations of m and taking the supremum over all possible partitions. (which are highly impractical assumptions for our purposes).

Intuitively, studying KS is a way of estimating how chaotic the properties of a dynamical system are (the larger KS , the less certainty we have in predicting the next cell upon further iterations of m). Now looking at the problem the other way around, we can go about establishing how non-ergodic the general map of chess is, and specially its dependency on initial condition.

5.5.2 How to compute it

So far our two main working partitions have been the partition by our reaction coordinate RC, and by the pawn structure. It may be easier to start with the partition via RC.

After each job, SPRES provides the time series of the occupation probability of each cell (or interface) and the transition probabilities between the cells. Given these two

pieces of information, we can start computing the probability $p(s)$ for all the possible sequences by

$$p(i_0, i_1, \dots) = \rho(i_0) \prod_{n=1}^N p(i_n \rightarrow i_{n+1}) \quad (5.3)$$

where $\rho(i_0)$ is the occupation probability of the cell i_0 . Then it remains to compute the corresponding H_S from which we would estimate KS.

On the other hand, if we want to compute KS for the \mathcal{M}_1 and \mathcal{M}_2 maps given the pawn structure partition, we fix the iteration length N , assume a subset of cells from which we draw our initial conditions, then we compute the respective $p(s) = p(i_0, \dots)$ of the observed symbolic sequences by counting the number initial conditions for which a given s has been observed.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

In this thesis, we studied the connectivity properties of the state space of chess using sampling techniques. More precisely, from a computational point of view, we showed that it is possible to perform efficient samplings between arbitrary positions. In terms of graph theoretic concepts, we proposed a random graph model for the state space of chess, and a flow network model for studying the connectivity of specific regions. Last but not least, various dynamical properties of chess were studied by decomposing the general map of chess into simpler ones. Moreover, we showed that by modelling chess in terms of statistical mechanics, certain aspects of its long term behaviour can be characterized in a manner analogous to certain physical systems, e.g. the motion of Brownian particles or the glassy phase of amorphous materials.

In view of the initial questions that were raised in the introduction, we can now safely say that stochastic rare event sampling techniques can be used successfully to sample the trajectory space of chess in an efficient manner in order to find paths that connect two positions under consideration. Moreover, regarding the question of whether or not a target position is reachable, we showed that by sampling a diverse and reasonably large subspace of positions, an acceptance criterion can be established from the reaction coordinate histogram of connected positions. This can serve as a reasonable first guess, specially useful for connectivity assessment of large subspaces.

Additionally, we showed that modelling subspaces of the state space of chess as random graphs, and studying their evolution and emergent topological properties, can unveil many interesting properties about the structure of the state space. For example, we observed that for subspaces comprised of randomly picked positions, i.e. no constraints on the opening or the structure, there is no formation of a large strongly connected component. Instead, the graph is mostly populated with isolated islands, with one critically large component if the edges are assumed to be undirected. Arguably, these

observations are to be expected for a such subspace, since the positions may have little in common in terms of their positional structure. Furthermore, the occurrence of a large component past the successful placement of ≈ 450 edges can be explained by the fact that positions in which only a few pawn moves have been made, remain compatible with a wide range of other pawn structures. But the reverse picture is not given due to the irreversibility of pawns, thus we do expect to see large components, but only in one direction, unless e.g. we consider a subspace of positions without pawns, or fixed pawn structure that leaves the other pieces highly mobile. Another irreversible aspect of the dynamics of chess is rooted in the capturing of pieces. Clearly, one can start from any position and gradually lose pieces, thereby connecting to many other positions that have a smaller piece count than the starting one. But again, the reverse is impossible as the only type of piece gain comes in the form of promotions, which itself comes at the cost of a pawn removal. Thus it is rather natural to not observe any critical changes in the size of the strongly connected component of the graph. Admittedly, so far, the study of the random graphs concerned only subspaces of random positions, whose evolution was studied up to 800 edges. Therefore, the observations made so far, should by no means indicate the end of the story.

Furthermore, by modelling the SPRES-sampled trajectory space between two regions under consideration as a flow network, we were able to assess the connectivity of the two regions in terms of the resilience of their network to losing vertices or edges. One of the advantages is that one does not necessarily have to go through the estimation of transition rates in order to make quantitative assessments about the connectivity of the two regions. Additionally, by computing the maximum flow, we can pinpoint the types of positions or connections (edges) that are responsible for the bottleneck of the transitions. From the point of view of chess theory, this can provide a very useful tool for studying the transpositions that exist between various opening lines. For example, by rating the most likely transpositions for each opening line and filtering out the implausible ones with a chess engine. For example, the Catalan and the English opening are known for their structural versatility as they can safely undergo many structural changes, thanks to the conservative development of pawns.

Regarding the study of the dynamics of chess, our most important observation was the strong dependence of the dynamics of chess on initial conditions, which rules out any hope for exhibiting ergodic behaviour in general. We showed that the main sources of non-ergodicity were: the irreversibility of pawns, the slow dynamics of pawns hemming the other pieces, the topological limitations of same color pieces (simply to say that they cannot ghost walk through one another), the irreversible reduction of the number of pieces and the finiteness of the board size. All of these lead to the following important consequences:

- When evolving the system under a number preserving map, the system (assumed to contain at least a certain number of pawns) can never become fully uncorrelated w.r.t. its starting position.
- For some initial conditions, the system was shown to exhibit different types of motion, with the subdiffusive regime being dominant.
- Even at low densities, some pieces remain highly localized, i.e. they remain unable to explore the whole board.
- Pathways tend to easily jam, even when attempting to connect similar positions.

Finally, rather interestingly, we saw that reactive paths are often highly order dependent, i.e. there is not much room in permuting the moves and still obtaining a valid reactive path. This is rather similar to optimal play of chess where there are only few specific sequences of moves that represent the best course of action, wherein by even a slight perturbation of the order, one can easily go from a completely winning situation to a losing one. In turn, the move order dependence of reactive paths can be explained by both the peculiar rules governing how each type of piece moves, as well as the interplay of irreversible and reversible pieces: pawns tend to dictate the evolution of the remaining (reversible) pieces. For example, if a pawn is moved too early, a bishop can be locked indefinitely into its own color's structure. On the other hand, if non-pawn pieces are developed first, they may also blockade the advancement of pawns towards the target position. These points lead to the following statement: Even to connect rather trivial positions, the reversible pieces undergo a lot of reshuffling in order to achieve the required structural change. However, the elements listed above, all contribute to lowering the chance of the required reshuffling taking place.

In closing, we have proposed and investigated various methods for both probing and assessing the connectivity properties of the state space of chess. Although we have partially answered many of the questions we initially set out to study, the work still remains part of an ongoing project, aimed at generalizing the results that were presented here.

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